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Prof. Romulus Gruia Ph. D.

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Editorial

Urban Regeneration and Tourism Development Strategy Braşov 2035

The speed of contemporary life is becoming daunting and requires the thinking of strategies for short and medium term with much precision, objectivity and professionalism.

Of course, there are concerns in this direction, such as the National Development Strategy of Romania (NDSR), the Axis of the Regional Operational Program (ROP), the Strategy of the Romanian Academy for Romania's development in the period 2016-2035, as well as various strategies at the level of the local communities. These are framework programs that can then provide punctual strategies, such as the concept of the development of Brasov having as a benchmark year 2035. Thus, the specificity of the place is placed in the foreground and the question is answered to a great extent: Does Braşov and its surroundings differ from other important localities together with their surrounding environment?

On the basis of the above mentioned, a strategy of urban regeneration and development, especially tourism, of Braşov can be envisaged over the next 20 years. In this sense, we consider that the originality of Braşov municipality can "extract its sap" from the perennial conceptual thread of the cultural-tourist axis. So:

- Brasov is distinguished by being the largest city in the entire Carpathian Mountains chain of the eight states belonging to this mountain system; is the area with the most trans-Carpathian movement; can be considered as the "capital of south-eastern mountain tourism";

- Brasov has the singularity of having a mountain in the middle of the city. The Time Mountain (Tempus / Tempa / Tampa, the city of Cronos: Kronstadt) is surrounded almost entirely by the city's neighborhoods, a mountain that can be specially arranged in the Natural Reserve (188 ha), extremely rare in the middle of a city, can become through specific arrangement the largest "Ecotourism Museum" in the world.

- Braşov presents the singularity of being the intersection or **node of the cardinal points of European spirituality**. It is the geographic center of Romania and in a radius of about 3500 km it is the center of a space with almost equal distances to the extreme points of Europe, namely the Atlantic to the west, the Ural Mountains to the east and to the important parallels of the Earth, respectively towards the North Polar Circle and to the Tropic of Cancer in the South. From this position, Braşov becomes the point of convergence of Europe in which three great tribes: the Latins, Germans and Slavs unite and complement each other.

It is the spiritual point with the Divine mission to harmonize latinity with the Slavonic world, the **North-South connection**, Catholicism with Protestantism, the scientific spirit with the creative-artistic spirit, and the Catholic world with the Orthodox in the **East-West connection**, ie the metaphysical preparation of a process divine emancipation and emergence, becoming in fact a "corpse" to another less stupid and criminal world. And not by chance these processes made possible the **genesis of the Romanian literary language** in Brasov, with the first writings in Romanian and translations from Slavonic, then Latin or German.

All these, and others, well-assembled and conceived, can undoubtedly constitute a conspicuous basis around which many complementary development projects with considerable strategic amplitude can be "woven" in the cultural and tourist area, having a maximum impact on the originality and uniqueness of Braşov , now, but by "sanding", especially at the level of 2035.

Director of the publication
Prof. Romulus Gruia, PhD, PhD Supervisor

SUMMARY

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PRELIMINARY RESEARCH ON THE CHARACTERISTICS OF PHENOLS IN *LAVANDULA ANGUSTIFOLIA SP.*

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Abstract: Starting from the fact that the European Pharmacopoeia allows the use for medicinal purposes only the flowers of *Lavandula sp.*, the main aim of this research was to investigate the chemical composition of *Lavandula angustifolia sp.* extracts obtained by three extraction methods: ultrasound-assisted extraction, rapid extraction under pressure at 6.7 bar and subcritical fluid extraction. The solvents used for the first two extraction methods were different mixtures of water and alcohol, glycerol or propylene glycol. These extracts were then analyzed for their qualitative composition by high performance thin layer chromatography, attenuated total reflection - Fourier transform infrared and Raman spectrometry as well, and for the total phenolic content using a modified Folin-Ciocalteu method. Subsequent high performance thin layer chromatography analyzes will highlight the main phenolic components in lavender extracts.

Keywords: *Lavandula sp.*, extraction, polyphenols, high performance thin layer chromatography.

1. Introduction

There is ample scientific evidence (Kaka et al. 2016) supporting that *Lavandula angustifolia* extract protected the neurons against glutamate toxicity (Büyükkokuroğlu et al. 2003).

In the last years the beneficial effects of lavender aqueous extract on spatial performance in Alzheimer's disease in rats was evaluated, as well (Kashani et al. 2011). Therefore, according with the evaluation made by the Committee of Herbal Medicinal Products of European Medicines Agency (EMA/HMPC/143183/2010), *Lavandula angustifolia* (as flower or leaves extract, and essential oil) has a lot of therapeutical properties, including antiseptic, anti-inflammatory, analgesic, cleansing, balancing, and soothing.

These studies have shown that lavender improve the free radical scavenging activity and reduce the stress hormone, cortisol, which protects the body from oxidative stress (EMA/HMPC/143183/2010; Atsumi and Tonosaki 2007).

The present research deals with the identification of the polyphenols responsible for antioxidant

activity of lavender extracts obtained by three extraction methods: ultrasound-assisted extraction, rapid extraction under pressure at 6.7 bar and supercritical fluid extraction. Six different extractive solutions were used for each extract performed using the first two methods. For supercritical fluid extraction 1,1,1,2-tetrafluorethane was used.

The best extracts, in terms of amount and stability of isolated phenolic total extracts were those obtained with supercritical fluid extraction method. This extraction method is a promising alternative to obtain the high amount of phenolic compounds. These phenolics are responsible for a good antioxidant activity and offer the possibility to use them in pharmaceutical formulations linked to the fields of nutrition, cosmetics and drugs (Hossu et al. 2006; Hossu et al. 2009).

2. Materials and methods

For obtaining the extracts, the dried lavender flowers *Lavandulae flos* from *Lavandula angustifolia* Mill. and *L. species* were chosen. The lavender flowers were cut in a plant cutting machine type Herbcut 1340, and dried in a

Miraco dryer with controlled temperature and humidity sensors that trigger the evacuation of humid air only after this moisture remains unchanged a programmable time. Further, dried lavender flowers were crushed in a mill, and then the raw material was sieved at 4 mm.

Ultrasound-assisted extraction was carried out using a Sonomatic Langford ultrasonic bath, equipped with the possibility to control the temperature of the solvent (35 °C) and ultrasonication time. Rapid extraction under pressure at 6.7 bar on lavender flowers was performed in a Timatic Micro C extractor at 35 °C. The extractive solutions used were as following: 50% water a (pH=5) – alcohol; 50% water b (pH=9) – alcohol; 50% water a (pH=5) – glycerol; 50%

water b (pH=9) – glycerol; 50% water a (pH=5) – propylene glycol and 50% water b (pH=9) – propylene glycol (see also Table 1). Waters (a) and (b) were obtained with a Kagen apparatus; glycerol and propylene glycol were of pharmaceutical grade.

Subcritical fluid extraction was performed by using a fluid extractor Timatic FC100, in which the volatile components and lipids were removed without affecting the water-soluble components which afterwards may be retrieved.

Table 1 summarizes the composition of the standards used for the identification of phenolics by thin-layer chromatography (continuing the studies in the follow-up stages).

Table 1. Standards used for the identification by high performance thin layer chromatography

Standard designation	Standard composition
S1	chlorogenic acid + gallic acid
S2	rutoside + hyperoside + isoquercitroside
S3	luteolin 7-O-glucoside
S4	vitexin + umbelliferone

3. Results and discussion

A first stage, since 2015, has been represented by the obtaining of extracts of fat soluble

bioactive compounds from lavender dry flowers within the *EBIOTEFA* Research Center from Transilvania University from Braşov, by extraction of subcritical fluids (fig.1).

a.

b.

c.

d.

Fig. 1. The extraction flow starting with lavender pay (a), diverse stages of extraction achieved with the equipment for extraction in fluids at subcritical pressure - the extractor of TIMATIC FC100 model (b) and the obtained extracts (c and d).

A first chromatographic analysis revealed the presence of main phenolic compounds in different amounts and/or composition in the lavender extracts according to the used extraction methods (i.e. ultrasound-assisted extraction, rapid extraction under pressure at 6.7 bar). By the procedure followed, it seems that the hydro-

alcoholic extraction, either with (a) or (b) water, results in more extracted compounds. The chromatograms (Figures 2 and 3) clearly show the presence of chlorogenic acid and umbelliferone in the hydro-alcoholic extracts (Rădulescu, Cristina et al, Valahia University of Targoviste).

Fig. 2. High performance thin layer chromatography image of selected chromatographic plates obtained for the extracts – visualized with ultraviolet light at 254 nm. Samples are named according to Table 1. Samples 1, 2, 7 and 8 were concentrated and samples 4 to 6 and 9 to 12 were concentrated and purified using silica gel cartridges (see main text). Standards are marked as following: C=chlorogenic acid; G=gallic acid; R=rutoside; H=hyperoside; I=isoquercitroside; L=luteolin 7-O-glucoside; V=vitexin; U=umbelliferone. The silica gel plate was developed with ethyl acetate: acetic acid anhydrous: formic acid: water (72:7:7:14) and derivatized with 2-aminoethyl diphenyl borate.

Fig. 3. High performance thin layer chromatography image of selected chromatographic plates obtained for the extracts – visualized with ultraviolet light at 365 nm. Samples are named according to Table 1. Samples 1, 2, 7 and 8 were concentrated and samples 4 to 6 and 9 to 12 were concentrated and purified using silica gel cartridges (see main text). Standards are marked as following: C=chlorogenic acid; G=gallic acid; R=rutoside; H=hyperoside; I=isoquercitroside; L=luteolin 7-O-glucoside; V=vitexin; U=umbelliferone. The silica gel plate was developed with ethyl acetate: acetic acid anhydrous: formic acid: water (72:7:7:14) and derivatized with 2-aminoethyl diphenyl borate.

High performance thin-layer chromatography analysis showed (Figures 1 and 2, Table 3) that the hydro-alcoholic extracts obtained by rapid extraction under pressure at 6.7 bar (samples 7 and 8), contain chlorogenic acid and umbelliferone in higher concentrations compared with the same extracts obtained by ultrasound-assisted extraction method (i.e. extracts 1 and 2). Isoquercitroside (3,3',4',5,7-pentahydroxi-3-beta-

D-glucufuranoside flavone) could be identified in all the extracts, except for samples 1 and 12.

The highest yield of total flavonoids from concentrated lavender extract obtained was obtained by supercritical fluid extraction. Good values was obtained for hydro-alcoholic lavender extract (i.e. extracts 7 and 8) obtained by rapid extraction under pressure at 6.7 bar (Table 2).

Table 2. *Qualitative analysis of total phenolic compounds in lavender extracts*

Sample	Total flavonoids [$\mu\text{g}/\text{mg}$ total extract]	
	Mean	Standard Deviation
Ultrasound-assisted extraction		
1	7.245	0.034
2	11.433	0.026
3	1.209	0.011
4	1.062	0.043
5	1.734	0.026
6	1.712	0.012
Rapid extraction under pressure at 6.7 bar		
7	32.673	0.804
8	31.972	0.756
9	1.562	0.018
10	1.762	0.012
11	1.145	0.024
12	1.435	0.035
Supercritical fluid extraction		
Extract in 1,1,1,2-tetrafluorethane	78.345	0.982

Conclusions

In the present study three types of extracts from flowers of *Lavandula angustifolia* sp. were prepared by different extraction methods (i.e. ultrasound-assisted extraction, rapid extraction under pressure at 6.7 bar and supercritical fluid extraction). The main phenolic compounds identified in analyzed extracts were as follows: chlorogenic acid, gallic acid, umbelliferone, luteolin 7-O-glucoside, vitexin and isoquercitroside (completing the studies will lead to the conclusion being finalized).

Acknowledgment

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References

- Atsumi, T., and K. Tonosaki. 2007. Smelling lavender and rosemary increases free radical scavenging activity and decreases cortisol level in saliva. *Psychiatry Res.* 150: 89-96;
- Barbes, L., C. Radulescu, C. Stih. 2014. ATR-FTIR spectrometry characterisation of polymeric materials. *Rom.Rep.Phys.* 66(3): 765-777;
- Bradley, B. F., N. J. Starkey, S. L. Brown, and R. W. Lea. 2007. Anxiolytic effects of *Lavandula angustifolia* odour on the Mongolian gerbil elevated plus maze. *J. Ethnopharmacol.* 111: 517-525;
- Büyükokuroğlu, M. E., A. Gepdiremen, A. Hacimüftüoğlu, and M. Oktay. 2003. The effects of aqueous extract of *Lavandula angustifolia* flowers in glutamate-induced neurotoxicity of cerebellar granular cell culture of rat pups. *J. Ethnopharmacol.* 84: 91-94;
- Capasso, R., A. A. Izzo, L. Pinto, T. Bifulco, C. Vitobello, and N. Mascolo. 2000

- Phytotherapy and quality of herbal medicines. *Fitoterapia*. 71: S58-S65;
6. Dinu, M., O. T. Olaru, A. Dune, C. Popescu, G. M. Nitulescu, and R. V. Ancuceanu. 2016. The Obtaining and Characterization of a Rich-phenolic Extract from *Amaranthus hypochondriacus* L. *Rev. Chim. Bucharest*. 67(5): 880-883;
 7. Gaceu L., Aspects regarding electrochemical detection of the antioxidant activity for subcritical extracts from *Pleurotus Ostreatus*, *Journal of EcoAgriTourism*, Vol. 13, no.1, 2017, pg. 53-57;s
 8. Gad, H. A., S. H. El-Ahmady, M. I. Abou-Shoer, and M. M. Al-Azizi. 2013. Application of chemometrics in authentication of herbal medicines: a review. *Phytochem. Analysis*. 24(1): 1-24;
 9. Gallego, M. G., M. H. Gordon, F. J. Segovia, M. Skowrya, and M. P. Almajano. 2013. Antioxidant properties of three aromatic herbs (rosemary, thyme and lavender) in oil-in-water emulsions. *J. Am. Oil Chem. Soc.* 90(10): 1559-1568;
 10. Hajhashemi, V., A. Ghannadi, and B. Sharif. 2003. Anti-inflammatory and analgesic properties of the leaf extracts and essential oil of *Lavandula angustifolia* Mill. *J. Ethnopharmacol.* 89: 67-71;
 11. Hossu, A. M., C. Radulescu, M. Ilie, D. Balalau, V. Magearu. 2006. Qualitative and semiquantitative TLC analysis of vitamins A, D and E. *Rev. Chim. Bucharest*. 57(11): 1188-1189;
 12. Hossu, A. M., M. F. Maria, C. Radulescu, M. Ilie, V. Magearu. 2009. TLC applications on separation and quantification of fat-soluble vitamins. *Rom. Biotech. Lett.* 14(5): 4615-4619;
 13. Huang, C. C. 2016. Applications of Raman spectroscopy in herbal medicine. *Appl. Spectrosc. Rev.* 51(1): 1-11;
 14. Kaka, G., K. Yaghoobi, S. Davoodi, S. R. Hosseini, S. H. Sadraie, and K. Mansouri. 2016. Assessment of the Neuroprotective Effects of *Lavandula angustifolia* Extract on the Contusive Model of Spinal Cord Injury in Wistar Rats. *Front Neurosci.* 10: Article ID 25, doi: 10.3389/fnins.2016.00025;
 15. Kashani, M. S., M. R. Tavirani, S. A. Talaei, and M. Salami. 2011. Aqueous extract of lavender (*Lavandula angustifolia*) improves the spatial performance of a rat model of Alzheimer's disease. *Neurosci. Bull.* 27: 99-106;
 16. Kasper, S., M. Gastpar, W.E. Müller, H.P. Volz, H.J. Möller, A. Dienel, and S. Schläfke. 2010. Silexan, an orally administered *Lavandula* oil preparation, is effective in the treatment of 'subsyndromal' anxiety disorder: a randomized, double-blind, placebo controlled trial. *Int. Clin. Psychopharmacol.* 25: 277-287;
 17. Koulivand, P. H., M. K. Ghadiri, and A. Gorji. 2013. Lavender and the Nervous System. *Evid Based Complement Alternat Med.* 2013: Article ID 681304. doi: 10.1155/2013/681304;
 18. Lu, Y., and L. Y. Foo. 2001. Antioxidant activities of polyphenols from sage (*Salvia officinalis*). *Food chem.* 75(2): 197-202;
 19. Margina, D., O. T. Olaru, M. Ilie, D. Grădinaru, C. Guțu, S. Voicu, A. Dinischiotu, D. A. Spandidos, and A. M. Tsatsakis. 2015. Assessment of the potential health benefits of certain total extracts from *Vitis vinifera*, *Aesculus hippocastanum* and *Curcuma longa*. *Exp. Ther. Med.* 10: 1681-1688;
 20. Olaru, O. T., L. Venables, M. van de Venter, G. M. Nitulescu, D. Margina, D. A. Spandidos, and A. M. Tsatsakis. 2015. Anticancer potential of selected *Fallopia Adans* species. *Oncol. Lett.* 10(3): 1323-1332;
 21. Radulescu, C., and C. Stihi. 2009. Biological activity of new heterocyclic systems containing thiazolic ring. *Rev. Chim. Bucharest*. 60(11): 1164-1168;
 22. Seremet, O. C., O. T. Olaru, M. Ilie, S. Negres, and D. Balalau. 2013. HPTLC evaluation of the pyrrolizidine alkaloid senecionine in certain phytochemical products. *Farmacina*, 61(4): 756-763;
 23. Woelk, H., and S. Schlafke. 2010. A multi-center, double-blind, randomised study of the Lavender oil preparation Silexan in comparison to Lorazepam for generalized anxiety disorder. *Phytomedicine*. 17: 94-99;
 24. Yaghoobi, K., G. Kaka, K. Mansouri, S. R. Hosseini. 2016. *Lavandula angustifolia* Extract Improves the Result of Human Umbilical Mesenchymal Wharton's Jelly Stem Cell Transplantation after Contusive Spinal Cord Injury in Wistar Rats. *Stem Cells Int.* 2016: Article ID 5328689, doi: 10.1155/2016/5328689.

INFLUENCE OF GREENHOUSES FORMS, LOCATED ON THE ROOFS OF BUILDINGS ON THE RESISTANCE TO WIND ACTION

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Abstract: *The paper highlights the importance that the current trend is manifested in the developed countries of Western Europe, USA, Japan etc., regarding the location of greenhouses for vegetables and flowers on the roofs of buildings, and the need they satisfy all the requirements imposed by Crops grown on ensuring environmental factors, those required by architects planners, but also those on the mechanical safety of the wind and bad weather they perform them at all times. Theoretical and experimental research conducted on 5 models of greenhouses showed the influence of the number of pitches roofs and angles they form these slopes over the forces of pressure / suction the wind at different speeds and directions exerts upon the strength structures of greenhouses, specifying in all cases of aerodynamic drag coefficient values of the respective forms of roofing.*

Keywords: *Greenhouses on the roof, mechanical strain, aerodynamic drag coefficient.*

1. Introduction

In the current period the construction of greenhouses located on the ground has become an attractive and highly competitive market, characterized by a high normalization and standardization. The general trend of making structures as safe in terms of resistance to mechanical stresses, overlaps with the need to reduce manufacturing costs, installation and equipping of greenhouses [7], but also with the rigorous selection of vegetables or flowers to cultivate so that the final product quality to live up to the highest level, and total spending to a minimum. Theoretical research and the practice have validated some constructive forms of greenhouses that have proven most effective. At the same time, free movement of products on the European market put before the committee specialized in Brussels circulation problems produced vegetables and flowers in greenhouses and construction of greenhouses question.

The first notable achievement in terms of building greenhouses unification is the minimization of distances between the rows of pillars, ie width sections, establishing the European Standard EN 13031-1 Greenhouse shape and construction. Part I: Commercial production greenhouses, CEN European Committee for Standardization (2001) Brussels, be 6.40 m, 9.60 m, 12.80 m and produce a typology of greenhouses for each of the intervals. For

greenhouse manufacturers is essential the existence of normative calculation and design through to optimize its structural capacity / cost. The methodologies provided for in the national regulations of the member countries in the European Union must respect the framework methodologies from Brussels, taking account of local conditions related to levels requests posed to those greenhouses. In Romania is used to design buildings with different shapes of roofs, and other structures with different uses Code Design Assessment of Wind on Buildings Indicative 1-1-4 CR / 2012. This bill is in turn placed permanently in line with European legislation and other standards that designers and builders of greenhouses on roofs must follow. The same applies to other countries, where construction standards are continuously updated, so as to make buildings more secure environmental factors, especially wind [3].

Like any law or standard nor code CR-1-1-4 / 2012 could not take into consideration all circumstances that could occur in practice. For this reason, in paragraph 1.4 aided design attempts to make the following clarifications:

1. For the evaluation the effect of wind on the building and its response may be used in the wind tunnel test results and / or numerical methods, using appropriate models and construction of the wind;

2. To conducting experimental attempts in the wind tunnel, wind action should be designed in a

manner that (i) the average wind velocity profile and turbulence characteristics in the construction site.

The greenhouses located on the roofs of buildings can not be confused with normal roofs, even though in some cases their shapes are close to them. The requirements that requires these greenhouse grown plants, on the materials to be used for the side walls and roofs, the existence of the necessary equipment and facilities to ensure growth factors, etc., makes these vulnerable construction elements to requests due to wind, snow formations earthquakes or their combined actions [5]. For the design and proper execution of these greenhouses, conducting further research it is not only useful, but even necessary.

The theoretical researches by simulation with finite element method and experimental research in the wind tunnel, models of greenhouses with shapes similar to those considered buildings with roofs typical respectively two and four slopes and angles between the limits in the Code were intended to pressure values available to designers / wind suction acting on rigid surfaces external forces such as pushing and overturning moments of drag coefficient of pressure / suction and force roof greenhouses with two four slopes. The speeds and wind drive directions were identical to theoretical and experimental research, and the similarities and differences between models of greenhouses offers designers the possibility of comparison and choice of the optimal solution for a given situation. On the other hand, comparing the results of theoretical and experimental research among themselves but also with the code entered in the CR-1-1-4 / 2012 aims to validate the research method adopted in this paper.

2. Material and Method

2.1 The aerodynamics resistance to wind action

A body moving from ambient air opposes a drag force F_d , proportional to air density ρ , with the front surface A of the body and the square of velocity relative to the body and air respectively.

F_d force called aerodynamic drag force and is calculated by equation (1): Following the evolution of the population in Romania, it can show that it follows the European trend as seen in Table 1 [27].

$$F_d = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \rho \cdot c_d \cdot A \cdot v_a^2 \quad (1)$$

where c_d is called coefficient of aerodynamic drag.

The drag coefficient c_d represent the influence body shape is the force exerted on the resistance to air and is determined experimentally [6].

This coefficient is not a constant, but varies depending on the speed, air flow direction, the position and size of the object, density and viscosity of air. Speed, kinematic viscosity and a characteristic length scale of the object are incorporated into a coefficient called dimensionless Reynolds number (Re). The compressible media, it is important to speed of sound, and the c_d is also dependent of the Mach number (Ma). For some form of body drag coefficient of c_d depends only on the number Re, Ma number and direction of the current. At low speeds coefficient of aerodynamic drag is no longer dependent on the Mach number. Also, for most areas of practical interest, the variation in Reynolds number is relatively small, so that for a flow of air having the same direction relative to the body examined, the coefficient c_d can be considered constant [11].

The aerodynamic forces on a body come mainly from differences in pressure and viscous shear stress. Thus, the aerodynamic drag force exerted on a body can be divided into two components, namely resistance due to friction (slip viscous) due to pressure and resistance (drag). In these cases, the coefficient of aerodynamic drag of a body placed in a flow of air is variable in its speed. [10] having a specific value for a given speed of the air stream [2].

The wind velocity is the main factor which determines and influences the aerodynamic drag force and can be measured accurately using anemometers. Visual estimation of wind speed can be done using the Beaufort scale (defined by Admiral Francis Beaufort in 1805), which has 12 degrees (0 ... 12), the latter being the hurricane, the wind speeds exceed 33m / s.

Air density is approximated in this paper to 1.225 kg / m³, its real value is influenced by temperature, humidity and air pressure.

2.2 Calculation and design of greenhouses located on the roofs of buildings using Code CR 1-1-4 / 2012

In accordance with the Code CR-1-1-4 / 2012 the buildings are divided into classes of importance-exposure, according to the human and economic consequences that may be caused by a natural hazard and / or major anthropogenic

and role their post-hazard response activities of the company. For the evaluation the effect of wind on buildings, each class of importance-exposure (I-IV) is associated with an exposure factor importantă-, g_{Iw} applied to its characteristic value. Values important factor - exposure, wind g_{Iw} actions are: $g_{Iw} = 1.15$ for the construction of important classes I and II-exposure; $g_{Iw} = 1.00$ for building class-important exposure III and IV.

The buildings equipped with greenhouses on roofs is better to be included in the class of importance-exposure immediately above normal building since the destruction of greenhouses under the action of winds can cause significant damage, including serious injury population.

The resulting pressure (total) of wind on a building component (eg a greenhouse built on a roof) is the difference between the pressures (oriented surface) and suction (targeted near

surface) on both sides of the element; to be taken with their signs. Pressures are considered the sign (+) and suction sign (-) as shown in Figure 1, which is a diagram exemplifying the building roof greenhouses studied similar models in theoretical and experimental work.

The force of the wind acting on a building / structure or of a structural element (for example, a greenhouse built on the roof) can be determined in two ways:

- as a global force, using aerodynamic coefficients of force;
- by adding pressure / suction acting on surfaces (rigid) of the building / structure, aerodynamic coefficients using pressure / suction.

Fig.1. Representation of the pressure / suction on surfaces in the Code CR-1-1-4 / 2012

The first version was used in this paper, that was determined experimentally global force with which the greenhouses of different shapes are pushed by air currents at different speeds and using the relation (1) were calculated coefficients aerodynamic force that characterizes a greenhouse of a some form.

To the theoretical and experimental investigations have included two strands wind to models of greenhouses, namely a front direction and lateral direction, as shown in the examples of code situation and CR-1-1-4 / 2012. Experimental investigations led forces push F_d

emissions for each model and knowing the reference area A in each case were calculated aerodynamic drag coefficient of c_d force.

The effects of air friction on surfaces will not be neglected to check the state of static equilibrium limit construction in question [12].

2.3 The aerodynamic coefficients of pressure / suction and force

The aerodynamic force coefficients are used to determine the overall strength of the wind on the structure (for example, a greenhouse), structural

element or component, including this effect and friction.

• *The aerodynamic coefficients of pressure / suction and force for roof with two slopes*

Four of greenhouses researched theoretical simulation and FEM three experimental models studied in the wind tunnel roofs with two slopes

are symmetrical, as shown in Figure 2. Between notations and values of tilt angles of roofs in Figure 2 and Tables 2-a and 2-b angles and scoring models researched correlation is as follows (Table 1).

Fig. 2. Notation for roofs with two slopes of the Code CR-1-1-4 / 2012

Table 1.

No. model	Notations in Figures 2 and 3 and in Tables 2 and 3	Notations on studied models (Table 4)
1.	35	110
2.	30	120
3.	45	90
4.	32,5	115
5.	40	100

The roof is divided into zones as shown in Figure 3. Exposure reference height, z_e is considered equal to h . The coefficients aerodynamic pressure / suction for each area are given in Tables no.3.

Both in theoretical research and the experimental results were studied airflow action with different speeds in two directions to the models considered, namely the front direction and lateral direction.

Table 2a

The angle of slope, a	Areas downwind $q = 0^\circ$									
	F		G		H		I		J	
	$C_{pe,10}$	$C_{pe,1}$	$C_{pe,10}$	$C_{pe,1}$	$C_{pe,10}$	$C_{pe,1}$	$C_{pe,10}$	$C_{pe,1}$	$C_{pe,10}$	$C_{pe,1}$
-30°	-0,6	-0,6	-0,6	-0,6	-0,8	-0,8	-0,7	-0,7	-1,0	-1,5
-45°	-1,1	-2,0	-0,8	-1,5	-0,8	-0,8	-0,6	-0,6	-0,8	-1,4
-15°	-2,5	-2,8	-1,3	-2,0	-0,9	-1,2	-0,5	-0,5	-0,7	-1,2
-5°	-2,3	-2,5	-1,2	-2,0	-0,8	-1,2	+0,2	+0,2	+0,2	+0,2
							-0,6	-0,6	-0,6	-0,6
5°	-1,7	-2,5	-1,2	-2,0	-0,6	-1,2	-0,6	-0,6	+0,2	+0,2
	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-0,6	-0,6
15°	-0,9	-2,0	-0,8	-1,5	-0,3	-0,3	-0,4	-0,4	-1,0	-1,5
	+0,2	+0,2	+0,2	+0,2	+0,2	+0,2	0	0	0	0
30°	-0,5	-1,5	-0,5	-1,5	-0,2	-0,2	-0,4	-0,4	-0,5	-0,5
	+0,7	+0,7	+0,7	+0,7	+0,4	+0,4	0	0	0	0
45°	0	0	0	0	0	0	-0,2	-0,2	-0,3	-0,3
	+0,7	+0,7	+0,7	+0,7	+0,6	+0,6	0	0	0	0
60°	+0,7	+0,7	+0,7	+0,7	+0,7	+0,7	-0,2	-0,2	-0,3	-0,3
75°	+0,8	+0,8	+0,8	+0,8	+0,8	+0,8	-0,2	-0,2	-0,3	-0,3

Table 2b

The angle of slope, a	Areas downwind $q = 90^\circ$							
	F		G		H		I	
	$C_{pe,10}$	$C_{pe,1}$	$C_{pe,10}$	$C_{pe,1}$	$C_{pe,10}$	$C_{pe,1}$	$C_{pe,10}$	$C_{pe,1}$
-45°	-1,4	-2,0	-1,2	-2,0	-1,0	-1,3	-0,9	-1,2
-30°	-1,5	-2,1	-1,2	-2,0	-1,0	-1,3	-0,9	-1,2
-15°	-1,9	-2,5	-1,2	-2,0	-0,8	-1,2	-0,8	-1,2
-5°	-1,8	-2,5	-1,2	-2,0	-0,7	-1,2	-0,6	-1,2
The angle of slope, a	Areas downwind $q = 90^\circ$							
	F		G		H		I	
	$C_{pe,10}$	$C_{pe,1}$	$C_{pe,10}$	$C_{pe,1}$	$C_{pe,10}$	$C_{pe,1}$	$C_{pe,10}$	$C_{pe,1}$
5°	-1,6	-2,2	-1,3	-2,0	-0,7	-1,2	-0,6	-0,6
15°	-1,3	-2,0	-1,3	-2,0	-0,6	-1,2	-0,5	-0,5
30°	-1,1	-1,5	-1,4	-2,0	-0,8	-1,2	-0,5	-0,5
45°	-1,1	-1,5	-1,4	-2,0	-0,9	-1,2	-0,5	-0,5
60°	-1,1	-1,5	-1,2	-2,0	-0,8	-1,0	-0,5	-0,5
75°	-1,1	-1,5	-1,2	-2,0	-0,8	-1,0	-0,5	-0,5

Note:

Marked angles of slopes are valid for theoretical and experimental models studied in the paper. Values marked the aerodynamic coefficients are matched against the results of experimental research

• **The aerodynamic coefficients of pressure / suction and force for roof with four slopes**

One of the models studied theoretically by simulation FEM and two of the investigated experimental wind tunnel had roofs with four slopes. One of the patterns is identical to the diagram of Figure 4, and the other four slopes has a symmetrical construction.

The roof is divided into zones as shown in Figure 3. The reference height, z_e is considered

equal to h . The coefficients aerodynamic pressure / suction for each area are given in Table 3.

On the model with two symmetrical roof with two slopes were analyzed pressures, forces, and aerodynamic coefficients for the front and side directions of the air stream to the position of the pattern. Model with four symmetrical slopes was considered one direction of the wind.

Fig.3. Notation for roofs with four slopes of the Code CR-1-1-4 / 2012 Wind direction

Table 3

The angle to slope a_0 for $q = 0^\circ$; a_{90} for $q = 90^\circ$	Areas downwind for $q = 0^\circ$ and $q = 90^\circ$																	
	F		G		H		I		J		K		L		M		N	
	$C_{pe,10}$	$C_{pe,1}$	$C_{pe,10}$	$C_{pe,1}$	$C_{pe,10}$	$C_{pe,1}$	$C_{pe,10}$	$C_{pe,1}$	$C_{pe,10}$	$C_{pe,1}$	$C_{pe,10}$	$C_{pe,1}$	$C_{pe,10}$	$C_{pe,1}$	$C_{pe,10}$	$C_{pe,1}$	$C_{pe,10}$	$C_{pe,1}$
5°	-1,7	-2,5	-1,2	-2,0	-	-1,2	-0,3	-0,6	-0,6	-1,2	-2,0	-0,6	-1,2	-0,4				
	0	0	0	0	0	0												
15°	-0,9	-2,0	-0,8	-1,5	-0,3		-0,5	-1,0	-1,5	-1,2	-2,0	-1,4	-2,0	-0,6	-1,2	-0,3		
	+0,2	+0,2	+0,2	+0,2	+0,2													
30°	-0,5	-1,5	-0,5	-1,5	-0,2		-0,4	-0,7	-1,2	-0,5	-1,4	-2,0	-0,8	-1,2	-0,2			
	+0,5	+0,7	+0,7	+0,4	+0,4													
45°	0	0	0	0	0		-0,3	-0,6	-0,3	-1,3	-2,0	-0,8	-1,2	-0,2				
	+0,7	+0,7	+0,7	+0,6	+0,6													
60°	+0,7	+0,7	+0,7	+0,7	+0,7		-0,3	-0,6	-0,3	-1,2	-2,0	-0,4	-1,2	-0,2				
75°	+0,8	+0,8	+0,8	+0,8	+0,8		-0,3	-0,6	-0,3	-1,2	-2,0	-0,4	-1,2	-0,2				

Note:

Marked angles of slopes are valid for theoretical and experimental models studied in the paper. Values marked the aerodynamic coefficients are matched against the results of experimental research.

2.4 The theoretical research by FEM simulation of influence form greenhouse on mechanical strain exerted by wind

The modeling and analysis CFD (Computational Fluid Dynamics) air flow greenhouses aims to determine the forces and moments acting on the greenhouse, forces and moments generated by the action of wind and air flow visualization forms the exterior surfaces of the greenhouse. To achieve this, using ANSYS 15.0 software, which is based on the finite element method [1].

The modelings and analysis refers to two types of greenhouses on the roof has 2 or 4 slopes symmetrical angles 110° , 120° , 115° , 100° and 90° from one another, a situation pursued further and experimental research, where they studied five models of greenhouses, which had the same arrangement of slopes acoperișurilor. Trebuie stated that the practice of constructive models validated those that are almost generalized crops of vegetables and flowers, offering environmental conditions satisfactory to the majority of plant species, but also resistance necessary to mechanical stress [4]. There will be two sets of research, one in front and one wind acting on the wind side of the acting position established by the Code conventional CR-1-1-4 / 2012.

The geometric design is shown in Figure 4, where the greenhouse is built in a field of type cuboid, an area where it is considered that there is air flowing at a speed of 10 m / s, 15 m / s, 20 m / s, 25 m / s, 27.5 m / s and 30 m / s, i.e. the same speed at which and experimental researches have been in the wind tunnel.

Fig. 4. The geometric design of the problem

For modeling is considered tetrahedral finite elements, meshing after yielding 257 826 finite elements and 48 559 nodes. Boundary conditions relate, on the one hand, imposing a constant speed in laminar flow at the entrance to the air flow and the imposition of 101.325 Pa normal atmospheric pressure in that area; the second condition refers to the imposition of border normal atmospheric pressure of 101.325 Pa at the outlet of the air flow.

As noted above, the analysis is performed for sets of values of wind speed of 10 m / s, 15 m / s, 20 m / s, 25 m / s, 27.5 m / s and 30 m / s, the front action and values of speed for the action of the air stream side.

Solving with finite element of the model involves selecting a number of iterations needed to stabilize calculating residual error. By choosing a sufficient number of iterations - 50 - stabilization of the residual error is obtained in both cases.

2.5 The experimental research of the influence of greenhouse form of the mechanical strain exerted by wind

The objects for experimental research are the five models of greenhouses (Figure 5), made of plastic with a thickness of 2.5 mm. In order to compare the results of experimental research among themselves but also with those of theoretical investigations, it was established that land bases and heights of all the models are identical, the differences between them consisting in the number of pitches roofs, angles thereof and useful volume.

The models with numbers 1, 2, and 3 have roofs made of two slopes (according to Figure 2 of CR 1-1-4 / 2012); model 4 is made up of four roof slopes (in accordance with Figure 3 of 1-1-4 CR / 2012), which forms a ridge, and the model no. 5 has roof slopes formed of four identical, forming a peak. Mockups to give sufficient rigidity to the action of wind, plastic panels were bolted profiles modeled on sheet thickness of 1.5 mm.

Since the tunnel is provided with 16 tubes with outer diameters of 3 mm used for measurement of the pressure exerted by the wind, the vertical walls and front side as well as the slopes of the roof have been applied in positions considered to be representative, a plurality of apertures with

diameters of 3 mm. The holes that have not been used to measure pressures were covered with adhesive tape.

Also, the measurement of thrust forces exerted by the wind on the models of all of the openings have been covered.

Fig. 5. *The greenhouses models developed for experimental research*

To all the models it was performed in the base plate by a hole with a diameter of 30 mm which were introduced into the models and were fixed in holes in the walls and roofs tubes for

measuring pressure / depression wind. Hole in the base plates served and fixing clips using appropriate layouts in the wind tunnel.

Table 4

Model no.	α_1^0	α_2^0	A_b, cm^2	H, cm	V, cm^3	A_{fv}, cm^2	A_{fac}, cm^2	A_{lv}, cm^2	A_{lac}, cm^2	A_t, cm^2
1.	110	-	400	20	6600	330	-	260	240	1660
2.	120	-	400	20	7000	350	-	300	220	1740
3.	90	-	400	20	6000	300	-	200	280	1560
4.	115	120	400	20	5600	250	80	250	180	1520
5.	100	100	400	20	5200	250	120	250	120	1480

The geometrical characteristics of the models used in experimental research are given in Table 4, the notations have the following meanings: α_1 - angle formed by the main slopes of the roof; α_2 - side slope angle of the roof; A_b -base area equal to all the models; H -înălțimea layout, equal on all models; V layout of the interior volume; A_{fv} vertical front wall area; Business frontal surface area of the roof; A_{lv} - vertical side wall area; A_{lac} -side roof surface area; A_t - area of the walls and roof.

It should be noted that the forms of the 5 models of greenhouses were not chosen by chance, they are the result of analysis of most forms of greenhouses that are currently being

used on the ground or on rooftops. Forms also means that not only meet environmental requirements for a large number of plants, but meeting and economically, meaning the use of materials and equipment available under the aspect ratio reliability / price being checked by practice.

The main tool used in experimental research has been wind tunnel HM170 Educational Wind Tunnel. G.U.N.T. Gerätebau GmbH. Barsbüttel, Germany [8] found in Wind Energy Laboratory for the Study of the Departamentului.de Product Design, Mechatronics and Environment at the

University of Braşov, whose general view is presented in Figure 6.

Fig. 6. HM 170 Aerodynamic Educational Wind Tunnel G.U.N.T. Gerätebau GmbH, Barsbüttel, Germany [11], [8]

This is a subsonic tunnel (air velocity up to Mach 0.1), the open-circuit (the outside air is taken in and expelled all the outside with higher speed. The area of measurement is the length of the section of 287x287 mm and 365 mm, it is made of plexiglass and superstructure moving longitudinally inserting and removing the models

subject experimental research.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. The measurement results of force exerted by the wind on the greenhouses superstructure

Table 5

Model \ Wind speed	10, m/s	15, m/s	20, m/s	25, m/s	27,5, m/s	30, m/s
1	4.0	9.0	11.6	13.2	14.4	15,9
2	4,0	8.6	11.4	13.2	14.2	15.8
3	3.6	7.8	11.8	13.0	14.8	16,0
4	3.4	7.0	10.2	12.6	13.0	14.4
5	3.4	7.4	11.2	12.8	13.6	15.2

Table 6

Model \ Wind speed	10, m/s	15, m/s	20, m/s	25, m/s	27,5, m/s	30, m/s
1	5.0	11.0	12,6	15.0	16.2	17.8
2	5.2	10.6	12,4	14.6	15.8	17.6
3	4.6	10.0	11,8	13.8	15.2	17.0
4	4.0	8.6	11,4	13.4	14.4	16.0
5	3.4	7.4	11,2	12.8	13.6	15.2

It notes that the the action front airflow layouts no. 1, no. 2 and # 3 opposing forces close enough resistance, especially at high wind speeds.

The smaller the pushing force was recorded, in the case of the front of the action of the wind, the model no. 4, which was about 12% lower than the mock-No. 3.

The model no. 5 thrust of frontal air stream was located at a mean value between the forces

pushing the first three models and thrust of the model no. 4.

If the action lateral of the air flow is an increase by 10 - 13% of pushing forces from the models no. 1, no. 2 and no. 3, the highest value recorded to model no. 1.

Increased thrust manifests and model no. 4, but the action and side air flow that is lower than the forces recorded in the first three models by over

10%.

Distinguished look are found in the action lateral airflow to model no. 5, pushing forces of resistance are identical to those found in front of this current action and are 15 ... 18% lower than the forces measured at the first three types of models.

3.2. Aerodynamic drag coefficient values at the push of the wind action

For the calculation of drag coefficient of resistance to the action of pushing the wind was used relation (1), where the air temperature T

= 18°C, barometric pressure p = 1026 mbarr and humidity 60%, air density has value $\rho = 1225 \text{ kg/m}^3$.

The aerodynamic drag coefficient c_d , calculated by equation (1), recommended in and the wind tunnel [9] and the forces pushing in Tables 5 and 6 are enrolled in Table 7 for each model layout and default speed of the wind action the frontal respectively in table 8 at its lateral action and in figures 7 and 8 plot the variations of these coefficients depending on the speed of the air flow.

Table 7

Model \ Wind speed	10, m/s	15, m/s	20, m/s	25, m/s	27,5, m/s	30, m/s	Mediu value
1	1.98	1.98	1.44	1.05	0.94	0.88	1.38
2	1.87	1.78	1.33	0.99	0.89	0.82	1.28
3	1.96	1.89	1.60	1.13	0.99	0.92	1.41
4	1.68	1.54	1.26	1.00	0.85	0.79	1.19
5	1.50	1.45	1.24	0.90	0.79	0.75	1.10

Fig. 7. The variation of aerodynamic drag coefficient of the models by frontal airflow action

Table 8

Model \ Wind speed	10, m/s	15, m/s	20, m/s	25, m/s	27,5, m/s	30, m/s	Medium value
1	1.63	1.60	0.98	0.78	0.70	0.65	1.05
2	1.63	1.48	0.97	0.74	0.66	0.62	1.02
3	1.56	1.51	1.00	0.75	0.68	0.64	1.03
4	1.51	1.45	1.08	0.81	0.72	0.68	1.04
5	1.50	1.45	1.24	0.90	0.79	0.75	1.10

Fig.8. The variation of aerodynamic drag coefficient of the models by lateral airflow action

Conclusions

Analyzing the results listed in Tables 7 and 8 and the graphic representations of Figures 7 and 8 shows the following:

- aerodynamic drag coefficients of the models subject experimental research falls within the limits listed in Tables 2a, b and 3 of the Code of Design Assessment of wind on buildings indicative 1-1-4 CR / 2012, the amounts recommended for roofs with two slopes (1.98 - 0.75 –at models, - 1.5 – 0.6- in the tables) and four slopes (- 1.51-0.63 at models ; -1.2- 0.5 ..- in the tables);

- for all the models examined, the coefficients of the front aerodynamic resistance to the action of the air stream with 20..25% are greater than the calculated action of the air stream side. No exception model. 5, the roof of four slopes is symmetrical, so that regardless of the wind direction coefficient of aerodynamic drag has the same value;

- if models no. 1, No. 2 and No. 3, with roofs of two slopes, the lowest coefficient of aerodynamic drag in front of wind action is manifested in

model no. 2, in which the angle of slope of the roof is the largest (120^0). Ascending No.1 and No.3 layouts are situated at angles of slopes are 110^0 , respectively 90^0 ;

- to the action lateral airflow lowest values of the coefficient of aerodynamic drag model posed no. 2. where the roof slopes are less inclined from the vertical inclinations compared to other models roofs;

- to the models no. 4 and no. 5 with four slopes roof aerodynamic drag coefficients in front wind action are 15..20% lower than in the models with two-pitch roofs; Instead, to the action of the wind lateral aerodynamic drag coefficients of these forms of greenhouses were higher than the roofs of two slopes;

- to the frontal wind action, model no. 5, the roof consists of four symmetrical slopes show the aerodynamic drag coefficient lower by 10% compared with those of the model no. 4, where the slopes are symmetrical two by two; instead, to the action of the wind lateral aerodynamic drag coefficients are lower in model no. 4 5 ... 10% less than the model no. 5.

References

- Badiu, E.C., Lateş, M.T., Brătucu, Gh.: *Simulation of the Solicitations to which Greenhouses Located on Rooftops are Subjected Based on Modeling with Finite Element Method*, în Bulletin of the Transilvania University of Brasov, VOL. 8 (57) No. 2– 2015, Series II – Forestry • Wood Industry • Agricultural Food Engineering, p. 61-68, ISSN 2065-2135 (Print), ISSN 2065-2143 (CD-ROM);
- Badiu, E.C., Lateş, M.T., Brătucu, Gh.: *Experimental Research on Determination of Drag Coefficient of the Greenhouses Located on Roofsof Buildings*, in Bulletin of the Transilvania University of Braşov • Series II • Vol. 9 (58) No. 1. 2016. p 43-50,

- ISSN 2065-2135 (Print), ISSN 2065-2143 (CD-ROM);
3. Badiu, E.C.: *Opinion: Cat Losses and when Building Codes, Design Fail*, in PROPERTUCASUALTY 360 DAILY ENEWS 28.08.2012, ALM Media Corporate HEADQUARTERS 120 Broadway 5th Floor New York, NY 10271, USA. (4.);
 4. Bodolan, C., Brătuțu, Gh. *Heat and Light Requirements of Vegetable Plants*, in the 5th International Conference "Computational Mechanics and Virtual Engineering " COMEC 2013, 24-25 October 2013, Brașov, Romania, Vol. 1, p. 361-364, ISBN 978-606-19-0225-5;
 5. Bodolan, C., Costiuc, L., Brătuțu, Gh.: *Greenhouse Energy Management Simulation Model*, in. Bulletin of the Transilvania University of Brașov • Series II • Vol. 9 (58) No. 1, 2016, p. 51-58 ISSN 2065-2135 (Print), ISSN 2065-2143 (CD-ROM);
 6. Greavu, V., Covaciu, D., ș.a.: *Eco-adăposturi modulare, dezvoltare de produs, Raport final privind efectul vântului*, Contract nr.464/17.04.2013, Operațiunea 0233-2011-1;
 7. Popescu, S., Ghinea, T.: *Automatizarea mașinilor și instalațiilor folosite în agricultură*, Editura Scrisul Românesc, Craiova, 1986;
 - 8***Equipment for Engineering Education. Operating Instructions. HM170 Educational Wind Tunnel. G.U.N.T. Gerätebau GmbH. Barsbüttel, Germany;
 - 9***Equipment for Engineering Education. Operating Instructions. HM170.23 Pressure Cylinder. G.U.N.T. Gerätebau GmbH. Barsbüttel, Germany;
 10. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Drag_coefficient, acces. 15.10.2015;
 11. <http://www.gunt.de>, acces 15.06.2016;
 12. <https://www.scribd.com/doc/.../CR-1-1-4-2012-Normativ-vant>, acces. 20.03.2014.

ASPECTS REGARDING THE TOURISTIC USE OF AGRICULTURAL RESOURCES FROM SOUTHERN DOBROGEA

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Abstract: Southern Dobrogea is a tableland area in South-Eastern part of Romania, between Danube and Black Sea Coast. The geographic location and quality of environmental factors have favored the development of diversified agricultural activities. The aim of this paper is to define the agricultural specific of the Southern Dobrogea territorial system, and its socio-economic efficiency by integrating in touristic activities. The research methodology is represented by bibliographic documentation, field research, statistical processing, and mapping using an open-source GIS program. There are highlighted the natural and socio-economic aspects of Southern Dobrogea territorial system, which by agri-tourism will contribute to sustainable development of the rural area.

Keywords: agriculture, environment, rural, sustainability, tourism

1. Introduction

Southern Dobrogea is a plateau unit in South-Eastern part of Romania and it represents a territorial system well outlined. The geographic analysis of this territory is essential in defining the type of regional and local development, considering some cultural and socio-economic achievements. The integrity and cohesion of the territorial system can be assessed by inter-conditionality of three components that govern its evolution: *the environmental component, the socio-cultural component, the economic and infrastructure component*. In order to do a correct diagnosis to status of the investigated territorial system, these are analyzed individually, but also in relation to each other [5].

The organization of geographical space within a territory must be analyzed from the point of view of the functional relationship between the resources and the possibilities for capitalizing through sustainable development scenarios, a support of population and its activities, with an essential role in the process of spatial planning [2,3].

The relationship between natural resources of the territory and their valorisation is the basis of any approach which aims the planning, also for agricultural and touristic purposes [3].

If the coastal zone is not included, the Southern Dobrogea territorial system has small touristic importance. However, there is any touristic potential, through the natural landscape,

apparently monotonous, but with specific elements on some areas, where the traditional folk art, historical and archaeological sites, and Dobrogea's villages could attract tourists [2,6].

The aim of this paper is represented by geographical analysis of natural resources of this territorial system, to define the agricultural potential and the possibility of valorisation for touristic purposes to the sustainability and the socio-economic efficiency of local communities in the rural area.

2. Material and Method

In order to identify the main geographical aspects of Southern Dobrogea were used bibliographic sources and cartographic documents. The first phase of work was to analyze and emphasize the physical-geographic aspects (geomorphologic, climatic, and soils conditions) and socio-economic aspects (the typology of human settlements, rural agricultural activities). Subsequently, were made cartographic documents (relief map, land use map) using an open-source GIS program [9]. In order to rank the administrative-territorial units by categories of agricultural potential with a possibility of touristic capitalization, it was made an evaluation of the agricultural, touristic and infrastructure resources, by its own methodology. For each criterion, specific indicators were analyzed, each of these being evaluated with a score from 1 to 5 (depending on potential), then by summing up to

a well-balanced value, as: the *agricultural resource* criterion - 50%, the *touristic resources* criterion - 40%, the *infrastructure* criterion - 10%.

The mapping to the geographic aspects of the natural heritage is very important to diagnosis and prognosis of the sustainable development of the rural area within Southern Dobrogea territorial system.

3. Results and discussions

Located between the Danube and the Black Sea, the Southern Dobrogea Plateau is a region of typical platform, and it has the largest area of all Dobrogea's parts, over 5,300 km². To East and West, the limits have a morpho-structural

character, following the Danubian steps, respectively, the Black Sea cliff (figure 1).

Agriculture is a traditional occupation in this territorial system. To favorable natural conditions, high fertility soils were added to sloping terrain, the construction of Carasu Irrigation System, and use of amendments, which allowed the development of crops, vineyards, fruit trees, and animal husbandry [1,6].

The plateau has an altitude with an average value of 75 - 100 m, being the lowest tableland from Romania. Although, it is said that Southern Dobrogea Plateau is tabular, and smooth as a plain, the tableland presents different orientation, slopes and fragmentation, waves and downsides.

Source: own figure

Fig. 1. Physical Map of Southern Dobrogea Territorial System

In Southern Dobrogea territorial system, the climate is temperate-continental, with sub-Mediterranean influences in South-West, semi-arid continental in rest, and moderate to the Danube and the Black Sea Coast. The specific

character of climate of Southern Dobrogea is climatic level of plain, with an average annual temperature of 11.0°C in West, to the Danube, and less than 11.0°C in the central part. In the warm season, from April to October, the average

temperatures are higher in peripheral areas, due to the influence of the Danube and Black Sea.

Rainfall decreases from West to East, from 450 to 400 mm, slightly higher in the higher areas of the plateau.

The most important climatic feature is the phenomenon of drought and dryness, all year long, affecting the agricultural activities [8].

In Southern Dobrogea, the hydrographic network is represented by ground waters from different geological deposits, and short rivers typical leakage through flow mode with intermittent character tributary to the Danube or Black Sea, and some fluvial or maritime lakes (figure 1).

The predominant vegetation is steppe, only in the South-West area being forests with diverse floral composition. The steppe vegetation occurs on small areas and is highly degraded of excessive grazing. Most of steppe has been replaced by agricultural crops. Forests are extended in South-West, in the highest part of the plateau.

The soil is strongly influenced by the dry climate, low slope topography, parent material consists predominantly of loess, steppe vegetation and ground water located at large depth. Following a relatively homogeneous soils factors, soils are just two classes: mollisol and undeveloped soils, soil types are arranged in strips according to arrangement of main features of relief.

Relief forms and soil quality on the fields had a great influence on the development of human settlements. The structure of rural settlements is generally gathered or scattered, with a tendency for gathering, in order to better use of outside lands, for agricultural crops [1,4].

As a basic economic activity for the population of Southern Dobrogea territorial system, **the agriculture** is a traditional occupation in this geographical area.

The natural conditions of environment (relief, soils, climate) and land planning (terracing of slopes, construction of Carasu irrigation system, and use of agricultural amendments) allowed the development of crops, vineyards, orchards and livestock [1,4,6].

The agricultural area extends to about 430,000 ha (80% of the territory of Southern Dobrogea Plateau). The structure of agricultural lands in Southern Dobrogea includes: 84% - arable lands, 10% - pastures, 4% - vineyards, and 2% - orchards (figure 2, figure 3) [10].

The arable lands have the largest weight in the Eastern half part of Southern Dobrogea, being predominantly cultivated with cereal crops (wheat, barley, corn), and sunflower crops. On small surfaces are cultivated other plants (leguminous and fodder plants) (figure 2).

Vineyards are extended on terraced slopes of valleys with land degradation. More than 45% of Southern Dobrogea vineyards are concentrated along Danube of Oltina Plateau, and over 35% along the Carasu Valley (Danube-Black Sea Canal) (figure 2, figure 3).

Orchards have expanded to the front of terraces, with degradation processes, and does not occupy large areas. Their structure is dominated of peaches and apricots. Over 60% of the total area of orchards is located along the Carasu Valley (Danube-Black Sea Canal), and over 16%, in the Western of the Oltina Plateau (figure 2, figure 3).

The high value of sunstroke in Southern Dobrogea, the exposure of terraced slopes, the quality of soils contribute to great productions of grapes, fruits and quality wines.

Natural grasslands (10% of the agricultural area), in relation to the fragmentation of relief and soil quality, are more extensive in South-Western part of the region, where is practiced the traditional pasture (figure 2, figure 3).

Animal husbandry as traditional occupation continues to be an important activity of agriculture. Natural grasslands, corn crops, and fodder crops have favored the development of a strong zootechnical sector.

Sheep farming, a traditional activity in Dobrogea's villages, occupies an important economic place for production of milk, dairy products, wool and meat.

Ensuring the consumption of meat, and meat products for human settlements of the Black Sea Coast is a stimulating factor for the intensive farming of pigs and poultry.

Beekeeping is a highly profitable economic activity, has seen a continuous development in this geographical area, which benefits of rich and varied melliferous flora.

The Southern Dobrogea territorial system comprises 45 rural administrative-territorial units.

Agri-tourism is a form of tourism, integrated in a framework that highlights the natural, cultural and human potential of a territorial system, where are being developed and promoted local touristic products, typically from rural environment.

Source: own figure

Fig. 2. Land Use Map of Southern Dobrogea Territorial System

Source: processed data, INSSE, 2016 [10]

Fig. 3. Agricultural Areas of Southern Dobrogea Territorial System

Thus, **the territory of Dobrogea's village** with its surrounding environment and its touristic resources are the support for agri-tourism, and agricultural resources will be the support for authentic and quality **agri-touristic products**.

The touristic resources from rural area of Southern Dobrogea territorial system are represented by: the Danube, Danubian lakes (Bugeac, Oltina, Dunăreni, Vederoasa), maritime lakes (Techirghiol, Tatlageac, Mangalia), Black Sea Coast, forests (Canaraua Fetii, Dumbrăveni, Esehioi, Fântânița-Murfatlar, Hagieni), and protected areas (Alah-Bair Hill, fossil points along Danube), monasteries (Derwent, Sf. Andrei, Sf. Teotim, Sf. Elena), historical sites (Tropaeum

Traiani, Păcuiul lui Soare), and archaeological sites (fortress along Danube: Capidava, Altinum, Sacidava), rural museums and traditional folk art (Cobadin, Limanu, Topalu), the multicultural specificity of Dobrogea's village (figure 1) [6,8].

Analyzing criteria of *agricultural resources*, *touristic resources* and *infrastructure*, the rural administrative-territorial units of Southern Dobrogea are ranked and grouped in four categories of valorisation of agricultural resources for touristic purpose: *high potential*; *medium potential*; *low potential*; *potential without touristic use* (table 1).

Table 1. Villages with agricultural resources for touristic use from Southern Dobrogea

Category	Indicators	Values	Villages
I - High potential (≥60.0%)	Agriculture (50%)	min.20 - max.36	Ostrov, Topalu, Rasova, Ion Corvin, Mihail Kogălniceanu, Lipnița, Cumpăna, Adamclisi, Cobadin, Oltina, Seimeni, Limanu, Aliman (13)
	Tourism (40%)	min.24 - max.34.4	
	Infrastructure (10%)	min.6 - max.8	
II - Medium potential (50.0-59.9%)	Agriculture (50%)	min.16 - max.32	Valu lui Traian, Peștera, Mircea Vodă, Crucea, Costinești, Dumbrăveni, Agigea, Ghindărești, Albești, Castelu (10)
	Tourism (40%)	min.24 - max.28	
	Infrastructure (10%)	min.4.4 - max.9.6	
III - Low potential (40.0-49.0%)	Agriculture (50%)	min.16 - max.24	Poarta Albă, Tuzla, Saligny, 23 August, Independența, Dobromir, Lumina, Horia, Deleni, Cuza Vodă, Pecineaga, Chirnogeni, Nicolae Bălcescu (13)
	Tourism (40%)	min.16.8 - max.24	
	Infrastructure (10%)	min.4 - max.8.8	
IV – Potential without touristic use (<40.0%)	Agriculture (50%)	min.16 - max.16	Amzacea, Siliștea, Ciocârlia, Topraisar, Tortomanu, Mereni, Comana, Cerchezu, Bărăganu (9)
	Tourism (40%)	min.15.2 - max.19.2	
	Infrastructure (10%)	min.4 - max.4.8	

For each criterion, were evaluated indicators such as: land use, crop production, livestock production, etc. (*agricultural resources* criterion); natural and cultural heritage (*touristic resources* criterion); utilities, transport network, accommodation, meals, leisure facilities, etc. (*infrastructure* criterion).

The results of evaluation were centralized in table 1, by mentioned categories. For the agricultural resources criterion, values resulted between 16.0 and 36.0 (the absolute value being 50), for the touristic resources criterion, values resulted from 15.2 to 34.4 (the absolute value being 40), for the infrastructure criterion, values resulted from 4.0 to 9.6 (absolute value being 10).

Thus, out of 45 rural administrative-territorial units analyzed, a number of 23 (50%) benefits of diversified agricultural resources with high potential, which could be associated with rural touristic activities. On the opposite side, 9 rural

administrative-territorial units (20%) have agricultural potential, but without touristic use.

The maximum concentration and optimal ratio of agricultural resources - touristic resources from Southern Dobrogea territorial system correspond to Danube sector between Ostrov and Topalu, with 8 villages (Ostrov, Topalu, Rasova, Ion Corvin, Lipnița, Oltina, Seimeni, Aliman), from 13 villages included in the 1st category of potential.

Other villages from 1st category are situated on the coastal area, more economic developed (Mihail Kogălniceanu, Cumpăna, Limanu), just Adamclisi village being an isolate case, but with a great agricultural and cultural-touristic potential.

Conclusions

1. The Southern Dobrogea territorial system has a high agricultural potential determined by its

geographical location and natural environmental conditions.

2. Local agricultural and touristic resources are partially capitalized due to poorly developed infrastructure, with the exception of Black Sea Coast area.

3. The diversity of agricultural resources from Southern Dobrogea can highlight different forms of agri-tourism: wine tourism, orchard tourism, api-tourism, gastronomic tourism, and farm tourism.

4. The optimal use of local agricultural and touristic resources by agri-tourism will lead the rise in living standards of inhabitants, protecting and preserving the environment, and socio-economic development of the Southern Dobrogea's village, based on sustainable principles.

5. Combining the customs and traditions of local communities with other agricultural and touristic resources will contribute to a bio-economic development with sustainable cultural and socio-economic valences of the rural area of Southern Dobrogea Territorial System.

References

1. Bordânc, Floarea: *Analiza regională a spațiului rural dobrogean*. București. Editura Universitară, 2008;
2. Câdea, Melinda, Bran, Florina: *Spațiul geografic românesc. Organizare-Amenajare-Dezvoltare durabilă*. București. Editura Economică, 2001;
3. Drăguț, L.: *Geografia peisajului*. Cluj-Napoca. Editura Presa Universitară Clujeană, 2000;
4. Guran-Nica, Liliana, Rusu, Marioara: *Probleme de geografie și economie rurală*. București. Editura Fundației România de Măine, 2004;
5. Ianoș, I.: *Sisteme teritoriale*. București. Editura Tehnică, 2000;
6. Iordan, I., Dobre, S. (coord.): *Podișul Dobrogei de Sud*. In: *Geografia României*, vol. V, București. Editura Academiei, 2005, p. 758-790;
7. Nicoară, V.: *Dobrogea. Regiune transfrontalieră europeană "Cadrilaterul"*. Constanța. Editura Muntenia, 2009;
8. Păltineanu, Cr., Mihăilescu, I. Fl., Seceleanu, I.: *Dobrogea. Condițiile pedoclimatice, consumul și necesarul apei de irigație ale principalelor culturi agricole*. Constanța. Editura ExPonto, 2000 ;
9. Urdea, Maria-Cornelia: *Using GIS techniques to identify analyse landscape. Case stud: the Măcin Mountains*. In: *Geographia Technica*, vol. 3(1), Cluj, 2008, p.135-140;
10. * * * *Anuarul Statistic al Judetului Constanta 2016*, www.insse.ro.

INHIBITORY EFFECT OF *CINNAMOMUM CASSIA* ESSENTIAL OIL AND HIS COMPONENTS ON DIFFERENT MICROORGANISMS

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Abstract: The antibacterial and antifungal potentials of cinnamon essential oil and two of his compounds (cinnamaldehyde and eugenol) were investigated in this study. For the antibacterial study were used two strains of bacteria *Escherichia coli* and *Proteus mirabilis* and for the antifungal study a yeast strain *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. The disk diffusion assay showed that *Cinnamomum cassia* oil and his major compound, cinnamaldehyde, have an important antibacterial and antifungal effect. We observed that this two have a major inhibitory effect against *E. coli* and *S. cerevisiae* while against *P. mirabilis* the inhibitory effect is less important. The eugenol has a low inhibitory effect against all three microorganisms. In conclusion *C. cassia* oil has an effectively inhibition effect over *E. coli* and *S. cerevisiae*.

Keywords: *Cinnamomum cassia* essential oil, Cinnamaldehyde, Eugenol, Inhibition, Disk diffusion assay, Bacterial growth curves;

1. Introduction

Cinnamon is a spice used for thousands of years and nowadays is one of the most used. In Europe cinnamon has appeared during the 16th and 17th centuries when the Portuguese found cinnamon in Sri Lanka.

The genus *Cinnamomum* (family *Lauraceae*) comprises over 300 aromatic evergreen trees and shrubs, located in almost all tropical regions of Earth. The most used species are *Cinnamomum zeylanicum* Blume (*Cinnamomum verum* J. Presl, Sri Lanka cinnamon or Ceylon cinnamon) and *Cinnamomum aromaticum* Nees (*Cinnamomum cassia* (L.) J. Presl, Chinese cinnamon or false cinnamon) due their multiple uses worldwide.

Cinnamon volatile oils are obtained from bark, leaves, flowers and buds.

The oil is a sweet yellowish liquid with a strong cinnamaldehyde taste. With time darkens to brown-red. The chemical composition of cinnamon oil varies depending on the part of the plant used for distillations process.

The main constituent of cinnamon bark oil is cinnamaldehyde, whereas eugenol is the main constituent of cinnamon leaf oil.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Chemicals

Cinnamon essential oil (*Cinnamomum cassia*) was purchased from MLW FRAGRANCE (Bonneuil sur Marne, France). Cinnamaldehyde, Eugenol were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA). All solutions were prepared in absolute ethanol. Working solutions were obtained from stock solution by serial dilutions. All the culture media components were purchased from either Biokar diagnostics (Allone, France) or Carlo Erba Reagents (Val de Reuil, France). Others chemicals used in this study were analytical grade and obtained either from Carlo Erba Reagents or Sigma-Aldrich.

2.2. Bacterial and yeast strains and growth conditions

Two strains of bacteria were used in this study: *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922 and *Proteus mirabilis* WT19 (corresponding to the clinical isolate U6450). These bacteria were grown in LB broth (Tryptone 10g/L, NaCl 10g/L, Yeast extract 5g/L, pH7) or LB agar plate (15g/L) at 37°C. The yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* strain used in this study was W303.1B and was cultivated on YPD medium (Tryptone 20g/L, Yeast extract 10g/L, pH7, Glucose 20g/L) or YPD agar plate (15g/L).

2.3. Bacterial growth curves

Growth curves were performed in 96 well plates. A 7-hours pre-culture was diluted to an $OD_{600nm, l=1cm} = 0.02$ in LB $((2,22 \pm 0,16) \times 10^6$ CFU/mL for *E. coli* and $(4,5 \pm 0,73) \times 10^6$ CFU/mL for *P. mirabilis*). 125 μ L of cell suspensions were inoculated in wells containing 125 μ L of cinnamon essential oil or cinnamaldehyde with a final concentration ranging from 81.7 to 413.6 μ g/mL or 78,8-399,9 μ g/mL.

The plates were incubated in a Polarstar Omega microplate reader (BMG Labtech, Ortenberg, Germany) at 37°C. $OD_{600nm, l=1mm}$ values were recorded every 15 minutes. Three replicates were performed for each concentration.

2.4. Disc diffusion assay

E. coli and *P. mirabilis* were cultivated in LB for 16 hours at 37°C and *S. cerevisiae* in YPD at 30°C. Cultures were adjusted to an $OD_{600nm, l=1cm} = 0.001$ $((1,11 \pm 0,08) \times 10^5$ CFU/mL for *E. coli*, $(2,25 \pm 0,36) \times 10^5$ CFU/mL for *P. mirabilis* and $(8,70 \pm 0,08) \times 10^7$ CFU/mL for *S. cerevisiae*) with sterile tryptone-salt Broth (Tryptone 1g/L, NaCl 8.5g/L, pH 7). 100 μ L of the bacterial and yeast suspensions were spread on LB agar or YPD agar. Filter paper discs (Whatman n°3, 7 mm in diameter) were incubated on the agar surface and soaked with 5 μ L of each dilution tested of *Cinnamom cassia* oil, cinnamaldehyde or eugenol

(0,5%, 1%; 2%, 4%, 8%, 10%, 12%, 16%, 20%, 25% which corresponds to 0,025; 0,05; 0,1; 0,2; 0,4; 0,5; 0,6; 0,8; 1; 1,25 μ L of tested compounds).

After 30min at room temperature, the plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours and respectively at 30°C for 48 hours for yeasts.

The diameters of the inhibition zones were measured in centimeters. Values are described as mean \pm SD as assays were performed in triplicates.

3. Results

3.1. Disc diffusion assay for antibacterial and antifungal activity of *C. cassia* oil

The antibacterial and antifungal activities (diameter of inhibition zone) of *C. cassia* oil, cinnamaldehyde and eugenol to *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922, *Proteus mirabilis* WT19 and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* W303.1B are summarized in Table 1, 2 and 3.

The inhibitory effect strengthened significantly with increasing amount of tested compound per disc. Discs with 5 μ L of 25% (v/v) *C. cassia* oil and cinnamaldehyde solution resulted in highest inhibition zones around 3-4 cm. Among tested bacteria, *E. coli* and *S. cerevisiae* are most sensitive to *C. cassia* oil and cinnamaldehyde.

Table 1. Inhibitory zone of different concentration of *C. cassia* oil against microorganisms (cm)

Cinnamon oil	Concentration (% V/V)										
	0	0,5	1	2	4	8	10	12	16	20	25
<i>E. coli</i>	1,10 $\pm 0,08$	1,31 $\pm 0,14$	1,41 $\pm 0,14$	1,47 $\pm 0,03$	1,51 $\pm 0,11$	2,11 $\pm 0,07$	2,43 $\pm 0,09$	2,68 $\pm 0,35$	2,93 $\pm 0,31$	3,23 $\pm 0,07$	3,86 $\pm 0,20$
<i>P. mirabilis</i>	0	0	0	0	0,75 $\pm 0,05$	1,41 $\pm 0,27$	1,75 $\pm 0,21$	2,2 $\pm 0,17$	2,6 $\pm 0,31$	2,78 $\pm 0,36$	3,31 $\pm 0,24$
<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	1,08 $\pm 0,12$	1,21 $\pm 0,08$	1,22 $\pm 0,10$	1,23 $\pm 0,03$	1,4 $\pm 0,32$	2,34 $\pm 0,18$	2,58 $\pm 0,10$	2,64 $\pm 0,14$	3,08 $\pm 0,17$	3,43 $\pm 0,20$	4,16 $\pm 0,15$

Table 2. Inhibitory zone of different concentration of Cinnamaldehyde against microorganisms (cm)

Cinnamaldehyde	Concentration (% V/V)										
	0	0,5	1	2	4	8	10	12	16	20	25
<i>E. coli</i>	1,10 $\pm 0,09$	1,23 $\pm 0,02$	1,31 $\pm 0,05$	1,35 $\pm 0,12$	1,43 $\pm 0,12$	2,11 $\pm 0,16$	2,36 $\pm 0,15$	2,56 $\pm 0,15$	2,87 $\pm 0,26$	3,5 $\pm 0,21$	4,07 $\pm 0,09$
<i>P. mirabilis</i>	0	0	0	0	0,93 $\pm 0,11$	1,6 $\pm 0,34$	1,75 $\pm 0,23$	2,43 $\pm 0,20$	2,83 $\pm 0,23$	3,08 $\pm 0,10$	3,4 $\pm 0,13$
<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	1,08 $\pm 0,08$	1,125 $\pm 0,02$	1,17 $\pm 0,03$	1,25 $\pm 0,05$	1,33 $\pm 0,13$	2,1 $\pm 0,16$	2,56 $\pm 0,31$	2,95 $\pm 0,07$	3,53 $\pm 0,15$	3,85 $\pm 0,07$	4,05 $\pm 0,07$

Table 3. Inhibitory zone of different concentration of Eugenol against microorganisms (cm)

Eugenol	Concentration (% V/V)										
	0	0,5	1	2	4	8	10	12	16	20	25
<i>E. coli</i>	1,08 ±0,08	1,13 ±0,02	1,21 ±0,06	1,25 ±0,15	1,43 ±0,09	1,46 ±0,11	1,49 ±0,02	1,5 ±0,1	1,78 ±0,16	2,2 ±0,2	2,4 ±0,11
<i>P. mirabilis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1,48 ±0,10	1,5 ±0,1	1,6 ±0,08	1,79 ±0,18
<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	0,98 ±0,08	1,1 ±0,05	1,18 ±0,10	1,18 ±0,02	1,18 ±0,08	1,2 ±0,17	1,21 ±0,19	1,4 ±0,08	1,63 ±0,20	1,8 ±0,2	2,13 ±0,11

Antibacterial activity of *Cinnamomum cassia* oil and compounds against *Escherichia coli* by disc diffusion method.

Fig. 1. Antibacterial activity of *Cinnamomum cassia* oil and compounds against *Escherichia coli* by disc diffusion method.

Antibacterial activity of *Cinnamomum cassia* oil and compounds against *Proteus mirabilis* by disc diffusion method.

Fig. 2. Antibacterial activity of *Cinnamomum cassia* oil and compounds against *Proteus mirabilis* by disc diffusion method.

Antibacterial activity of *Cinnamomum cassia* oil and compounds against *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* by disc diffusion method.

Fig. 3. Antibacterial activity of *Cinnamomum cassia* oil and compounds against *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* by disc diffusion method.

Table 4. Antibacterial activity of *C. cassia* oil, cinnamaldehyde and eugenol against microorganisms by disc diffusion method. Representative disc diffusion image. Antimicrobial activity was determined by forming a clear zone around the disc

3.2. Bacterial growth curves

We observe that the lowest concentration of *C. cassia* oil and cinnamaldehyde, 0.0079% (v/v), increased the lag phase of all tested bacteria. At the concentration of 0.016% (v/v), *C. cassia* oil

delayed the log phase of *E. coli* for about 8 h. *C. cassia* oil at the concentration of 0.02% (v/v) or above completely inhibited the growth of *E. coli*, while for *P. mirabilis* is 0.016(v/v) or above. The cinnamaldehyde completely inhibited the growth

of *E. coli* and *P. mirabilis* from a concentration of 0,025% (v/v).

E. coli growth curve in presence of different concentrations of *Cinnamomum cassia* oil (V/V)

Fig. 4. Growth curves of *E. coli* in LB broth containing different concentrations of *C. cassia* oil

Proteus mirabilis growth curve in presence of different concentrations of *Cinnamomum cassia* oil (V/V)

Fig. 5. Growth curves of *P. mirabilis* in LB broth containing different concentrations of *C. cassia* oil

Fig. 6. Growth curves of *E. coli* in LB broth containing different concentrations of cinnamaldehyde

Fig. 5. Growth curves of *P. mirabilis* in LB broth containing different concentrations of cinnamaldehyde

Conclusions

The disk diffusion assay showed that *Cinnamomum cassia* oil and his major compound, cinnamaldehyde, have an important antibacterial and antifungal effect. We observed that this two have a major inhibitory effect against *E. coli* and *S. cerevisiae* while against *P. mirabilis* the inhibitory effect is less important. The eugenol has a low inhibitory effect against all three microorganisms.

From the growth curves we observe that *C. cassia* oil and cinnamaldehyde have an inhibitory

effect using very low concentrations but is the cinnamon oil that has the most important antibacterial effect. The results suggest that *C. cassia* oil and cinnamaldehyde can be used as natural antimicrobial agents in food industry.

References

1. Amalaradjou, M.A.R., Narayanan, A., Baskaran, S.A., Venkitanarayanan, K., (2010) Antibiofilm effect of trans-cinnamaldehyde on uropathogenic *Escherichia coli*. *J. Urol.* 184, 358–363;

2. Becerril, R., Nerin, C., & Gomez-Lus, R. (2012). Evaluation of bacterial resistance to essential oils and antibiotics after exposure to oregano and cinnamon essential oils. *Foodborne Pathogens and Disease*, 9(8), 699-705;
3. Cava, R., Nowak, E., Taboada, A., & Marin-Iniesta, F. (2007). Antimicrobial activity of clove and cinnamon essential oils against *Listeria monocytogenes* in pasteurized milk. *Journal of Food Protection*, 70(12), 2757-2763;
4. Gill, A.O., Holley, R.A., (2004) Mechanisms of bactericidal action of cinnamaldehyde against *Listeria monocytogenes* and eugenol against *L. monocytogenes* and *Lactobacillus sakei*. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 70, 5750–5755;
5. Gulsun Akdemir Evrendilek, G. A., Empirical prediction and validation of antibacterial inhibitory effects of various plant essential oils on common pathogenic bacteria. *International Journal of Food Microbiology* 202 (2015) 35–41;
6. Hili, P., Evans, C. S., & Veness, R. G. (1997). Antimicrobial action of essential oils: the effect of dimethylsulphoxide on the activity of cinnamon oil. *Letters in Applied Microbiology*, 24(4), 269-275;
7. Hong, Y. J., Bae, Y. M., Moon, B., & Lee, S. Y. (2013). Inhibitory effect of cinnamon powder on pathogen growth in laboratory media and oriental-style rice cakes (sulgidduk). *Journal of Food Protection*, 76(1), 133-138;
8. Jayaprakasha, G. K., & Rao, L. J. (2011). Chemistry, biogenesis, and biological activities of *Cinnamomum zeylanicum*. *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition*, 51(6), 547-562;
9. Kima, Y., Lee, J., Kimb, S., Baek, K., Lee, J., Cinnamon bark oil and its components inhibit biofilm formation and toxin production. *International Journal of Food Microbiology* 195 (2015) 30–39;
10. Mau, J., Chen, C., & Hsieh, P. (2001). Antimicrobial effect of extracts from Chinese chive, cinnamon, and corni fructus. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 49 (1), 183-188;
11. Mayaud, L., Carricajo, A., Zhiri, A., Aubert, G., Comparison of bacteriostatic and bactericidal activity of 13 essential oils against strains with varying sensitivity to antibiotics. *Letters in Applied Microbiology* 47 (2008) 167–173;
12. Mith, H., Remi Dure, R., Delcenserie, V., Zhiri, A., Georges Daube, G., Clinquart, A., Antimicrobial activities of commercial essential oils and their components against food-borne pathogens and food spoilage bacteria. *Food Science & Nutrition* 2014; 2(4): 403–416;
13. Ooi, L. S., Li, Y., Kam, S. L., Wang, H., Wong, E. Y., & Ooi, V. E. (2006). Antimicrobial activities of cinnamon oil and cinnamaldehyde from the Chinese medicinal herb *Cinnamomum cassia* Blume. *American Journal of Chinese Medicine*, 34(3), 511-522;
14. Sheng, L., Zhu, M., (2014). Inhibitory effect of *Cinnamomum cassia* oil on non-O157 Shiga toxin-producing *Escherichia coli*. *Food Control* 46 (2014) 374-381;
15. Sienkiewicz, M., Głowacka A., Kowalczyk, E., Wiktorowska-Owczarek, A., Józwiak-Bębenista, M., Łysakowska, M., The Biological Activities of Cinnamon, Geranium and Lavender Essential Oils. *Molecules* (2014), 19, 20929-20940;
16. Wang, R., Wang, Rj, Yang, B., Extraction of essential oils from five cinnamon leaves and identification of their volatile compound compositions. *Innovative Food Science and Emerging Technologies* 10 (2009) 289–292.

CONSIDERATION REGARDING FOOD TEXTURE ANALYSIS AND ITS INFLUENCE ON CONSUMER BUYING DECISION

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Abstract: *The texture of food is one of the important factors contributing to subconscious perception of quality sensory properties. Based on this we see that the education of consumer is an important factor in the acceptance or refusal of food products. If the prior education determine the consumer to anticipate the food product by sensors induced by subconscious, the product will be accepted by the consumer without any objections from the sensors but if the contrary, the feeling is not in conformity with the comfort induced by subconscious, the product will not go unnoticed and may even lead to a denial of food product. The properties of texture can make a difference on quality in terms of processing technologies and food categories such as organic, traditional and conventional food products.*

Keywords: *texture, human sensors, quality, prior education.*

1. Introduction

Food consumption is influenced by several factors such as quality, price, and marketing. In the category of quality, the main characteristics of the product are related to the way that consumer perceives the product through the sensory capacities available to him through the sense organs (hearing, seeing, smelling) that offer an organoleptic analysis followed by a sensory analysis of the texture properties involving the oral cavity as an organ. Texture is an important factor in the appreciation of food products and most people seem to have a clear idea of the expected texture of a product based on their memory of past experiences (Mojet, 2005).

Consumer education is very important or even decisive when it comes to accepting a product or other product, so rural consumers seem to know better the differences between organic and conventional products than urban consumers.

The texture of food varies depending on the mode and the degree of processing, thus favoring different consumer appraisals. In order to identify in the research the link between sensory analysis and texture properties of organic, conventional and traditional foods, have been considered less processed products such as raw products.

2. Materials and method

-Sample of 150 people, students, aged 19-25;
-30 organic products on the Romanian market;

-30 traditional Romanian products;
-30 conventional products on the Romanian market;

-Keyence VHX600 digital microscope.

Methods:

- Sensory analysis designed to appreciate texture properties;
- Microscopic analysis using the Keyence VHX 600 digital microscope.

In the sensory analysis of the texture properties were considered as parameters: (Necula et al. 2013);

Rigidity- as an indicator of analysis- the compression force of the product between the molar teeth;

Adhesion - as an indicator of analysis- the degree of adherence of the product to the teeth;

Masticability - as an indicator of analysis- the number of cyclic mastication movements required to form the food bowl;

Toughness -as an indicator of analysis- the number of mastications required to disintegrate the product to be swallowed (Luca, 2014).

The experimental researches were carried out at the High Tech Research Innovation Development Institute for Sustainable Development of the Transilvania University from Brasov, Romania.

3. Results and discussion

Working hypothesis 1

The prior education is very important in consumer choice of food products.

The food consumer education (Kahnman, 2012) is an important form of influence on its perception when he purchasing food because this is based on sensory experience of food acquired over the years from childhood to maturity.

In order to highlight the importance of the consumer's prior education towards food products, a questionnaire was made on a group of 30 people aged 25-60 years, with secondary and higher education, representatives from local institutions in Romania. Consumers who participated in this questionnaire have had one thing in common; they came from rural areas, are living or lived in the village.

Following the analysis of the questionnaire responses, I came to the conclusion that these consumers have better criteria in order to choose products compared to those who came from urban areas, this consumers have better criteria based on taste and texture in order to differentiate organic products from conventional ones.

Working hypothesis 2

Texture properties of foods are an important criterion in the consumer's decision in order to accept or refuse the food.

Before that 150 people from urban areas to be part of the sensory food research, they had to respond to a questionnaire asking: What kind of

food do you prefer - A food that requires a greater effort of mastication? Or a food that requires less exercise?

The answers were in favor of the second question, which demonstrates the importance of texture properties in consumer choice.

To the question: What kind of meat do you prefer: dishes made from commercial meat or meat products from the traditional producers? The answer was in favor of commercial preparations because the texture of meat in case of commercial preparations is finer and easier to chew compare to traditional products.

In order to find an explanation of the answer to these questions, several food products have been analyzed in the sensory analysis for different degrees of importance of the texture (Rus, 2001) in relation to their quality. The relationship between the importance of texture and the quality of products perceived by the consumer is dependent on the degree of processing of the product. Thus, an ultra-processed product may be more preferred by consumers at the expense of a less processed product with a simpler recipe, since the higher degree of processing involves less effort on the part of the consumer in the mastication process.

In order to understand the importance of texture in choosing products by consumers, have been considered raw products, which have undergone few changes during their traceability, such as conventional honey, in figure 1 and figure 2.

Fig.1. Rape honey –IJ9523

Fig.2. Rape honey -IJ7215

For the sensory analysis of texture properties was choosed two sample of rape honey IJ9523 and IJ7215 from diferent producers because of its

solid consistency witch could not be differentiated with the help of the sense- see organ. As a result of the sensory analysis (Necula

et al, 2013) of the texture properties, the sample from the fig.2 was preferred by consumer. The reason for choosing this sample is the finer consistency compared to the other product.

Working hypothesis 3

The texture properties differ for the three categories of food: organic, conventional and traditional. How does this decision influence the consumer?

In the case of traditional products, texture properties can not be distinguished on the same principle as organic products because we can not

speak of a traditional raw material, but a traditional way of processing that gives the product the attribute of traditional product. Microscopic analysis of traditional products compared to organic or conventional products cannot be based on the principle of equality in the presentation of these products.

In order to comply with this principle, in the comparative microscopic analysis as well as comparative sensory analysis were analyzed raw products belonging to the two categories of conventional and ecological products, as shown in figures 3 and 4.

Fig.3. *Conventional tomatoes-section*

Fig.4. *Ecological tomatoes-section*

From the category of raw products, fresh fruits and vegetables were chosen for analysis, the quality of these products being dependent on the perception of the texture properties by the consumer.

From the point of view of the texture properties, on the principle of preference, conventional tomato was chosen.

Fig.5. *Ecological bananas*

Fig. 6. *Conventional bananas*

Ecological tomatoes, was considered more rigid than conventional tomatoes. Not the same thing happened in the case of appreciation of taste and smell, this time ecological tomatoes was the most appreciated product. Besides vegetables, fruits are another category of raw products that can be consumed in unprocessed form and whose qualitative (Marculescu, 2001) appreciation depends greatly on the texture properties.

One of the most commonly consumed fruits are bananas, although sensory analysis makes it difficult to distinguish between an organic product and a conventional one, microscopically can see changes as shown in figures 5 and 6 below.

Conclusions

The sensory experience of healthy and qualitative products such as organic products can form in the mind of the consumer a reference model for every subsequent sensory experience in food commodities, so that a prior education can be developed in the case of comparative analysis.

The texture of food is perceived as an indicator for the quality of food in the consumer's subconscious. For each category of food, the consumer has an own standard for assessing the quality of the food according to the mode and the degree of processing. So all the texture properties that can be interpreted by rigidity-adhesion-masticability-toughness are dependent on each other and this represents a criteria in acceptance or rejection by consumers based on education, lifestyle, and age.

The texture properties differ for the three categories of conventional, organic and traditional food. These differences may be to the advantage or disadvantage of a product of the three categories, this fact must draw the attention of the producers of organic and traditional products to consumer education because the consumer in generally tends to focus on slightly chewable products, a criterion which includes conventional product.

References

1. Hoerr, J., Fogel, J., Benjamin Van Voorhees, 2017: Ecological correlations of dietary food intake and mental health disorders., *Journal of Epidemiology and Global Health* (2017) 7, 81– 89
2. Jeltema, M., Jacqueline Beckley , Jennifer Vahalik, 2016: Food texture assessment and preference based on Mouth Behavior ., *Food Quality and Preference* 52 (2016) 160– 171;
3. Kahnman, D., 2012: *Thinking fast and slow*, Editura Penguin Books Ltd.;
4. Luca, Loredana, 2014: *Certificarea produselor ecologice*, Universitatea Transilvania, Facultatea de Alimentație și Turism;
5. Mărculescu, Angela, 2001: *Managementul calității produselor agro-alimentare*, Editura Universității "Transilvania" din Brașov.
6. Mojet, J., Koster, E.P., 2005: Sensory memory and food texture., *Food Quality and Preference* 16 (2005) 251–266;
7. Necula, V., Babii, Mihaela, 2012: *Analiza senzorială a alimentelor și produselor alimentare*, Editura Universității "Transilvania" din Brașov;
8. Necula, V., Babii, Mihaela, Marina, Aneta, 2013: *Analiză senzorială*, Editura Universității „Transilvania” din Brașov;
9. Risso, S.D., Cristina Giuliani, Antinucci, M., Gabriella Morini, Garagnani, P., Tofanelli, S., Donata Luiselli, 2017: A bio-cultural approach to the study of food choice: The contribution of taste genetics, population and culture. *Appetite* 114 (2017) 240e247;
10. Rus, Fl., 2001: *Bazele operațiilor din industria alimentară*, Editura Universității „Transilvania” din Brașov;
11. * <http://www.ifoam-eu.org/en/romania>;
12. * <http://www.madr.ro>;
13. * <http://biocerttraditional.ro>.

OPERATIONAL MANAGEMENT OF SANOGENEOUS NUTRITION. CASE STUDY COVASNA COUNTY

O.B. OPREA

Abstract: *The paper presents the benefits of bread with grape seed flour, because of its nutritional properties. There was made a case study in Covasna County, taking into account the calculation of the material balance, the choice of the necessary equipment and their location in the production unit. The need for final products was calculated starting from the number of tourists that check in into the Mercur hotel and the number of patients that are using the facilities of the heart hospital, and their need of bread consumption.*

The calculations show the sustainability of the chosen technological solution, which can be applied in medium or large size units.

Keywords: *sanogeneous, functional food, grape seed, nutrition;*

1. Introduction

For each category of food there are several practical and useful ways to measure portions that provide sufficient amounts of essential nutrients for the body without predisposing to fattening. Normally, the amount of calories needed in a woman's diet is 2,000 kilocalories, and in men 2,500 kilocalories. A 500g bread contains about 2,000 kilocalories, so it has concluded that the bread requirement per person per day is 170 g, which means 680 kilocalories. [11, 13].

According to the above-mentioned data, there was made a statistic, of which it has been found out that, on average, in all the hotels in Covasna, 5,820 tourists are checked in, including 1,400 during the week and 4,420 at the end of the week, and 20,400 of people per month at the hospital. Starting from the fact that a person requires 170 g of bakery product per day for a balanced diet, during the week's travel for 71 people at hotels and 680 people at the hospital it is needed 127.670 g of bakery product per day and at end of week 190.740 g of bakery product / day of weekend. So in a month, we get a total of 2,553,400 g of bakery product / weekly, 1,907,400 g of finished product / weekend, totaling 4,460,800 g of product per month.

Product range:

- White bread- 500 g
- White bun- 50 g
- Bread from grape seed flour- 500 g
- Bun from grape seed flour- 50 g

2. Management elements in sanogeneous nutrition

Calculation of material balance

Daily production: 100 kg

Ingredients used in the dough production in% for 100 kg.

Preparation of raw materials for 74 kg flour:

$$T_{MP} = C_F + C_D + C_S + C_A + C_{FSS}$$

Where:

T_{MP} – the amount of raw material [kg];

C_F – the amount of flour [kg];

C_D – the amount of yeast [kg];

C_S – the amount of salt [kg];

C_{FSS} – the amount of grape seed flour [kg];

C_A – the amount of water [kg];

$$T_{MP} = 66,6 + 1,71 + 1,3 + 7,4 + 47$$

$$T_{MP} = 124,01 \text{ kg}$$

Raw material dosage:

$$T_{MPA} = A_{MPA}$$

Where:

T_{MPA} – the amount of raw material [kg];

A_{MPA} – raw material mixture [kg];

$$124,01 = 124,01 \text{ kg.}$$

Dough kneading:

$$A_{MPA} = C_{AF}$$

Where:

A_{MPA} – raw and auxiliary material mixture [kg];

C_{AF} – the amount of kneaded dough [kg];

$$124,01 = 124,01 \text{ (Kneaded dough);}$$

Dough fermentation:

$$C_{AFE} = C_{AF} - P_{FE}$$

Where:

C_{AFE} - the amount of dough resulting from the fermentation process [kg];

C_{AF} - the amount of kneaded dough [kg];

P_{FE} - losses from the fermentation process [kg];

$P_{FE} = 1\%$

$P_{FE} = 1\% * C_{AF} = 1\% * 124,01 = 1,24 \text{ kg}$

$P_{FE} = 1,24 \text{ kg}$

$C_{AFE} = 124,01 - 1,24 = 122,76 \text{ kg}$
(Fermented dough)

Dough processing:

$C_{APR} = C_{AFE} - P_{PR}$

Where:

C_{APR} - the amount of dough resulting from processing [kg];

C_{AFE} - the amount of dough resulting from the fermentation process [kg];

P_{PR} - losses from processing [kg];

$P_{PR} = 2\%$

$P_{PR} = 2\% * C_{AFE} = 2\% * 122,76 = 2,45 \text{ kg}$

$P_{PR} = 2,45 \text{ kg}$

$C_{APR} = 122,76 - 2,45 \text{ kg} = 120,28 \text{ kg}$

Dough baking process:

$C_{PF} = C_{APR} - P_C$

Where:

C_{PF} - the quantity of final product resulting from the baking process [kg];

C_{APR} - the amount of dough resulting from processing [kg];

P_C - losses during the baking process [kg];

$P_C = 5\%$

$P_C = 5\% * 120,28 = 6,01 \text{ kg}$

$P_C = 6,01 \text{ kg}$

$C_{PF} = 120,28 - 6,01 = 114,27 \text{ kg}$
(Final product)

Bread cooling process:

$C_{PR} = C_{PF} - P_R$

Where:

C_{PR} - the amount of final product resulting from the cooling process [kg];

C_{PF} - the quantity of final product resulting from the baking process [kg];

P_R - losses resulting from cooling process [kg];

$P_R = 3\%$

$P_R = 3\% * 114,27 \text{ kg} = 3,42 \text{ kg}$

$P_R = 3,42 \text{ kg}$

$C_{PR} = 114,27 - 3,42 \text{ kg} = 110,85 \text{ kg}$
(Final cooled product)

Packing - Storage:

$C_{PA-D} = C_{PR} - P_{A-D}$

Where:

C_{PA-D} - the amount of final product resulting from the packing-storing process [kg];

C_{PR} - the amount of final product resulting from the cooling process [kg];

P_{A-D} - losses from packing-storing process [kg];

$P_{A-D} = 0,2\%$

$P_{A-D} = 0,2\% * 110,85 = 0,22 \text{ kg}$

$P_{A-D} = 0,22 \text{ kg}$

$C_{PA-D} = 110,85 - 0,22 = 110,63 \text{ kg}$
(Packed and stored final product)

Specific consumption:

-for white wheat flour:

$CS = 1/R * 66,6 = 1/110,85 * 66,6 = 0,6 \text{ kg/kg bread}$

-for yeast

$CS = M/R = 1,71/110,85 = 0,015 \text{ kg/kg bread}$

-for water

$CS = M/R = 47/110,85 = 0,42 \text{ kg/kg bread}$

-for salt

$CS = M/R = 1,3/110,85 = 0,01 \text{ kg/kg bread}$

-for grape seed flour

$CS = M/R = 7,4/110,85 = 0,06 \text{ kg/kg bread}$

Technological efficiency:

$R = (100 + MA) - (PF + PA + PC + PR + P)$

Where:

MP - raw materials;

PF - losses during the fermentation process;

PA - losses during processing;

PC - losses during baking;

PR - losses during cooling;

P - losses resulting from packing-storing process;

$P_{FE} = 1\% * C_{AF} = 1\% * 124,01 = 1,24 \text{ kg}$

$P_{PR} = 2\% * C_{AFE} = 2\% * 122,76 = 2,45 \text{ kg}$

$P_C = 5\% * 120,28 = 6,01 \text{ kg}$

$P_R = 3\% * 114,27 \text{ kg} = 3,42 \text{ kg}$

$P_{A-D} = 0,2\% * 110,85 = 0,22 \text{ kg}$

$R = (66,6 + 1,71 + 1,3 + 7,4 + 47) -$

$(1,24 + 2,45 + 6,01 + 3,42 + 0,22)$

$R = 124,01 - 13,34$

$R = 110,67/74 \text{ kg flour}$

Preparation of raw materials for 100 kg of finished product:

$T_{MP} = C_F + C_D + C_S + C_A + C_{FSS}$

Where:

T_{MP} - the amount of raw material [kg];

C_F - the amount of flour [kg];

C_D - the amount of yeast; [kg]

C_S - the amount of salt [kg];

C_{FSS} - the amount of grape seed flour [kg];

C_A - the amount of water [kg];

$T_{MP} = 60,17 + 1,54 + 1,17 + 6,68 + 42,46$

$T_{MP} = 112,03 \text{ kg}$

Raw material dosage:

$T_{MPA} = A_{MPA}$

Where:

T_{MPA} – the amount of raw material [kg];

A_{MPA} – raw material mixture [kg];

$$112,03 = 112,03 \text{ kg.}$$

Dough kneading:

$$A_{MPA} = C_{AF}$$

Where:

A_{MPA} - raw and auxiliary material mixture [kg];

C_{AF} - the amount of kneaded dough [kg];

$$112,03 = 112,03 \text{ (kneaded dough);}$$

Dough fermentation:

$$C_{AFE} = C_{AF} - P_{FE}$$

Where:

C_{AFE} - the amount of dough resulting from the fermentation process [kg];

C_{AF} - the amount of kneaded dough [kg];

P_{FE} – losses resulting from fermentation process [kg];

$$P_{FE} = 1\%$$

$$P_{FE} = 1\% * C_{AF} = 1\% * 112,03 = 1,12 \text{ kg}$$

$$P_{FE} = 1,12 \text{ kg}$$

$$C_{AFE} = 112,03 - 1,12 = 110,91 \text{ kg}$$

(Fermented dough)

Dough Processing:

$$C_{APR} = C_{AFE} - P_{PR}$$

Where:

C_{APR} - the amount of dough resulting from processing [kg];

C_{AFE} - the amount of dough resulting from the fermentation process [kg];

P_{PR} – losses resulting from processing [kg].

$$P_{PR} = 2\%$$

$$P_{PR} = 2\% * C_{AFE} = 2\% * 110,91 = 2,21 \text{ kg}$$

$$P_{PR} = 2,21 \text{ kg}$$

$$C_{APR} = 110,91 - 2,21 \text{ kg} = 108,7 \text{ kg}$$

Dough baking process:

$$C_{PF} = C_{APR} - P_C$$

Where:

C_{PF} – the quantity of final product resulting from the baking process [kg];

C_{APR} - the amount of dough resulting from processing [kg];

P_C – losses resulting from baking process [kg].

$$P_C = 5\%$$

$$P_C = 5\% * 108,7 = 5,43 \text{ kg}$$

$$P_C = 5,43 \text{ kg}$$

$$C_{PF} = 108,7 - 5,43 = 103,27 \text{ kg (Final product)}$$

Bread cooling process:

$$C_{PR} = C_{PF} - P_R$$

Where:

C_{PR} – the amount of final product resulting from the cooling process [kg];

C_{PF} – the quantity of final product resulting from the baking process [kg];

P_R – losses resulting from cooling process [kg];

$$P_R = 3\%$$

$$P_R = 3\% * 103,27 \text{ kg} = 3,09 \text{ kg}$$

$$P_R = 3,09 \text{ kg}$$

$$C_{PR} = 103,27 - 3,09 \text{ kg} = 100,18 \text{ kg}$$

(Cooled final product)

Packing-storing process:

$$C_{PA-D} = C_{PR} - P_{A-D}$$

Where:

C_{PA-D} – the amount of final product resulting from the packing-storing process [kg];

C_{PR} – the amount of final product resulting from the cooling process [kg];

P_{A-D} – losses resulting from the packing-storing process [kg];

$$P_{A-D} = 0,2\%$$

$$P_{A-D} = 0,2\% * 100,18 = 0,2 \text{ kg}$$

$$P_{A-D} = 0,2 \text{ kg}$$

$$C_{PA-D} = 100,18 - 0,2 = 99,98 \text{ kg}$$

(Packed and stored final product)

Specific consumption:

-for white wheat flour

$$CS = 1/R * 66,86 = 1/99,98 * 66,86 = 0,66 \text{ kg/kg bread}$$

- for yeast

$$CS = M/R = 1,54/99,98 = 0,015 \text{ kg/kg bread}$$

- for water

$$CS = M/R = 42,46/99,98 = 0,42 \text{ kg/kg bread}$$

- for salt

$$CS = M/R = 1,17/99,98 = 0,01 \text{ kg/kg bread}$$

- for grape seed flour

$$CS = M/R = 6,68/99,98 = 0,06 \text{ kg/kg bread}$$

Technological efficiency:

$$R = (100 + MA) - (PF + PA + PC + PR + P)$$

Where:

MP – raw materials;

PF – losses during the fermentation process;

PA – losses during dough processing;

PC – losses during baking;

PR – losses during cooling;

P – losses during packing-storing;

$$P_{FE} = 1\% * C_{AF} = 1\% * 112,03 = 1,12 \text{ kg}$$

$$P_{PR} = 2\% * C_{AFE} = 2\% * 110,91 = 2,21 \text{ kg}$$

$$P_C = 5\% * 108,7 = 5,43 \text{ kg}$$

$$P_R = 3\% * 103,27 \text{ kg} = 3,09 \text{ kg}$$

$$P_{A-D} = 0,2\% * 100,18 = 0,2 \text{ kg}$$

$$R = (60,17 + 1,54 + 1,17 + 42,46 + 6,68) -$$

$$(1,12 + 2,21 + 5,43 + 3,09 + 0,2)$$

$$R = 112,02 - 12,05$$

$$R = 99,99/66,86 \text{ kg flour}$$

Table 1. Quantities of bakery products manufactured per month [1]

Unit	Occupancy rate during the week	Occupancy rate at the end of the week	Gram product/day during the week	Gram product/day at the end of the week	Gram product /month during the week	Gram product /month at the end of the week	Total product/month
HOTEL	71	442	12.070	75.140	241.400	751.400	4.460.800
HOSPITAL	680	680	115.600	115.600	2.312.000	1.156.000	
TOTAL	751	1.122	127.670	190.740	2.553.400	1.907.400	

Table 2. Monthly production [1]

Product	Gram product/ pcs	Gram product/day during the week	Total pcs/day during the week	Gram product/day at the end of the week	Total pcs/day at the end of the week	Gram product/month during the week	Total pcs/month during the week	Gram product/month at the end of week	Total pcs/month at the end of the week	Total pcs of product/month
White bread	500	26.172	52	39.102	78	523.447	1.047	391.017	752	1.799
White bun	50	37.663	753	56.268	1.125	753.253	15.065	562.683	11.254	26.319
Bread from grape seed flour	500	26.172	52	39.102	78	523.447	1.047	391.017	752	1.799
Bun from grape seed flour	50	37.663	753	56.268	1.125	753.253	15.065	562.683	11.254	26.319
Total		127.670		190.740		2.553.400		1.907.400		

Table 3. Material balance [1]

Raw materials	Quantities for 74 kg flour (110,67 kg final product/ 74 kg flour)		Quantities for 100 kg final product	
	Amounts in U.M.	Quantities in %	Quantities in U.M.	Quantities in %
Wheat white flour	66,6 kg	90	60,17 kg	90
Grape seed flour	7,4 kg	10	6,68 kg	10
Compressed yeast	1,71 kg	1,71	1,54 kg	1,71
Salt	1,3 kg	1,3	1,17 kg	1,3
Water	47 L	47	42,46 L	47

Table 4. Raw materials for bakery products from grape seed flour and wheat white flour [6]

Type	U.M.	Quantity	Price [lei/Kg]	Value (lei)
Wheat white flour	Kg	1.342,03	1,15	1.543,33
Grape seed flour	Kg	148,99	27,40	4.082,32
Compressed yeast (Pakmaya)	Kg	34,35	4,6	158,01
Salt	Kg	26,1	0,35	9,13
Water	L	946,13	2,9/m ³	2,74
TOTAL		2.497,6		5.795,53

Table 5. Raw materials for bakery products from wheat white flour [6]

Type	U.M.	Quantity	Price [lei/Kg]	Value (lei)
Wheat white flour	Kg	1.491,02	1,15	1.714,67
Compressed yeast (Pakmaya)	Kg	34,35	4,6	158,01
Salt	Kg	26,1	0,35	9,13
Water	L	946,13	2,9/m ³	2,74
TOTAL		2.497,6		5.795,53

Table 6. Consumables [2]

Type	U.M.	Quantity	Price [Lei]	Value [Lei]
Thermal insulating cotton gloves up to 200 ° C to remove products from the oven. A pack of 10 pcs	buc	1	50	50
White coats	buc	2	10	20
Brushes	buc	4	15	60
Disposable lid of white thin vlies, for food industry 100 pcs	buc	1	28	28
Paper napkins, 21.5 x 25 cm, 200 pieces / set, green	buc	2	3,72	7,44
Plastic boxes for transporting bread with a capacity of 25pcs of bread of 500g/box*	buc	335	15	5.025
Diesel**	L	150	4,24	636
TOTAL			106,72	801,44

* It was calculated that 335 plastic vessels will be need because of the total quantity of bread, 5% will not be transported but will be produced for the restaurant, so from the 3,598 pieces produced 3,418 pieces will be transported, for which 135 vessels are required and 180 will remain for the Mercury Restaurant. Of the 52,638 buns, 50,006 will be transported to the other

hotels and the cardiology hospital, which requires 200 crates and 2,632 buns will stay at the hotel.

** It is assumed that the loaded car has an average consumption of 9L /100km and 7L not loaded. By delivering in the Covasna resort daily, the driver makes 50 km, it is calculated an average of 5 l of fuel per day, so the monthly fuel consumption is 150 liters [10].

Table 7. Fixed asset depreciation (purchase value>2500 lei)

Name	Purchase value	Quantity	Duration of liquidation (years)	Monthly liquidation
Flour sifter type SF100	12.780,64	1	10	106,50
Agitator with fixed tank type SILVER 50	7.858,64	1	10	65,48
Hydraulic divider type sq20	28.989,67	1	10	241,58
Fermentation type TELBO	19.347,89	1	10	161,22
Steam oven type RING model MSR 4	58.535,43	1	10	487,79
Car for transport (Volkswagen Transporter T5)	17.855,1	1	5	297,58
TOTAL	301.986,27	1		1360,15

3. Technical and constructive elements regarding the establishment of a bakery factory with sanogeneous products. Case study covasna balnear network

In the balnear network of Covasna sanogenic foods could be approached, which have positive effects in the following cases: allergies, bronchial asthma, rheumatism, dermatological diseases; neurosis, insomnia, psychosomatic diseases; parasitosis, chronic infections, viral diseases; Chronic intoxication, hypercholesterolemia; gastro-duodenal ulcer, enterocolitis, biliary dyskinesia; deficiencies in vitamins and minerals; states of exhaustion and stress [15].

The Covasna balnear resort is a complex tourist product, competitive on the domestic and foreign tourism market. It is an internationally renowned balnear resort; Covasna is situated at an altitude of 564 m at the foot of the western slope of the Brețcu Mountains, in the southern part of Târgu Secuiesc, 31 km from Sfântu Gheorghe and 60 km from Brasov.

Due to the specific geological conditions, Covasna is rich in springs of various mineral waters and natural CO₂ emissions. In 1882, mineral water from the Horgasz spring was awarded at Trieste. Researches made over time

by specialists and researchers, as well as the results of balnear treatments, have permanently imposed Covasna among the most important health facilities [18].

So Covasna is a balnear resort with a tradition of treating cardiovascular diseases with natural factors: carbonated mineral water, natural mofetes (post-volcanic carbon dioxide emissions), as well as rich in negative aerosols, due to the forests from surroundings.

The variety of natural cleansing agents as well as facilities in the treatment base, offer the possibility of simultaneous treatment of several diseases, which confers the great complexity of the resort [10].

The "MERCUR" complex in Covasna belongs to a large investor in Bucharest, TTS (Transport Trade Services) SA, which was built and put into use in the beginning of December 2015, with a special architecture designed to accommodate Romanian and foreign tourists, and treatment base.

The hotel's maximum capacity is 57 rooms. And because business tourism is practiced, the hotel also offers a specially designed meeting and event space, two conference rooms (100 seats) with adequate facilities.

Table 8. Calculation of the surface required for storing the raw material

Raw materials	Specific upload	Needed upload
Flour, Grape seed flour	650 kg/m ²	5m ²
Yeast	120kg/m ³	1 m ³
Salt	150 kg/m ²	1 m ²
TOTAL		9 m ²

The constructive solution chosen in terms of both the construction and the products is to achieve the objectives related to:

- Introducing an innovative product on the market, namely bread from grape seed flour;
- Daily production of 52 pieces (26,172 g) of 500 g white bread, 753 pieces of white bread bun 50 g (37,663 g) the same quantities of bread from grape seed flour products during the week, and at the end of the week, production of a total of 78 pieces of white flour bread of 500 g (39,102 g), 1,125 white bread buns of 50 g (56,268), respectively 78 pieces of grape seed flour bread (39,102 g) and 1,125 grapes seed flour buns (56 268g);
- Allows sufficient work space;
- The machines are located in accordance with the manufacturing process and the space

between the machines varies according to the working process of the machine, the space required for the maneuvers.

The following machines and equipments are presently in the restaurant's kitchen [9]:

1. TED-AF14EKOMTN Double refrigerated cabinet - capacity 1400 l;
2. FKR-GN600FISH Refrigerated cabinet for fish - GN2/1;
3. TED-AF07EKOMTN Refrigerated cabinet - capacity 700 l;
4. TED-AF07EKOMTN Freezer cabinet - capacity 700 l;
5. TED-TF02EKOgn Cold table with 2 doors - capacity 310 l;
6. VES-FKG371 Vertical refrigerating cabinet - capacity 35 l;

7. TED-TF03EKOgn Cold table with 3 doors - capacity 400 l;
8. MET-TAVR/20 Hot-ventilated cupboard;
9. TED-AF06EKOMTTNPV Refrigerated cabinet - capacity 600 l;
10. EUT-ST805ST2 Dishwasher - SteelTech18-00;
11. TED-TF04EKOgn Cold table with 4 doors - capacity 620 l;
12. ANG-FX101E3 Mixed electric oven capacity 10 trays GNII;
13. ANG-190TP0 - Gas cooker;
14. COZ-BTEB718H Hot bain-marie mass - capacity 5xGNII;

15. ANG-190FT2G - Fry-top gas supply surface striated;
16. ANG-190GRG BBQ with ceramic rock;
17. ANG-091FR3E Electric fryer;
18. ANG-091FRIG Gas feed fryer;
19. Vessels, utensils, machinery.

Thus, the mini factory has a total of 120 m² of which:

- Storage space of raw materials: 12 m²;
- Production department: 77 m²;
- Final product cooling section: 1.8 m²;
- Final product storage space: 12 m²;
- Dressing room: 11 m²;
- Bathroom: 3 m²;

Fig. 1. Mini factory outline. Mercur Hotel [6]

Conclusions

Bread is a common food product in almost all the world's societies.

Prepared bread from grape seed flour is considered a functional food and has the following benefits for human health:

- Antioxidant;
- Self-destruction of cancer cells;
- Detoxification;
- Protects joints;
- Stimulates anabolism;
- It is recommended to use it in special diets (for weight loss, for diabetics, for people with heart problems).

Considering the technology of bread making with the addition of grape seeds, the economic calculations required for the implementation were carried out in a public food unit in Covasna. This is intended, on the one hand, for the in-house consumption of hotel and restaurant customers, and on the other hand it provides products for the medical units in the area and for those with different health problems.

The calculations show the sustainability of the chosen technological solution, which can be applied in medium or large size units.

Layout area of bakery mini factory

Fig. 2. Ground floor Mercur Hotel [16]

References

1. Boian N., *Diagnosticul întreprinderilor de turism*, Editura Universității Transilvania din Brașov, ISBN 978-606-19-0412-9;
2. Gaceu L., *Utilaje și tehnologii în panificație*, note de curs;
3. Gaceu, L.; Gruia, R., Education in food and tourism area using moodle management courses system in Transilvania University of Brasov, Journal of EcoAgriTourism 2009 Vol.5 No.1 pp.43-49;
4. Gaceu L., Hygienic engineering and design in Romania, Journal of EcoAgriTourism 2016 Vol.12 No.2, pg. 154-159;
5. Dumitru Mnerie, Liviu Gaceu, Oleksii Gubenia, Mark Shamtsyan, Adriana Birca, Gabriela Victoria Mnerie, Comparative study on the evolution of the food labeling quality in some countries from the Black Sea region, Journal of Hygienic Engineering and Design, pg. 60-65, 2016;
6. Mărculescu A., *Biochimia produselor alimentare*, Carmen Liliana Bădărău, Editura Universității Transilvania din Brașov;
7. Mărculescu A., *Managementul calității produselor agro-alimentare*, Editura Universității Transilvania din Brașov, ISBN 978-973-598-860-9;
8. Țane N., *Instalații și echipamente în hoteluri și restaurante*, Editura Universității Transilvania din Brașov;
9. <https://biblioteca.regielive.ro/referate/marketing/statiunea-covasna-247946.html>;
10. http://rjmp.com.ro/articles/2011.2/PM_Nr-2_2011_Art-6.pdf;
11. <https://www.proiecte.ro/industria-alimentara/tehnologia-fabricarii-painii-si-a-produselor-de-franzelarie-si-simigerie-58074>;
12. <https://foodnews.ro/strugurii-materie-prima-pentru-vinificatie/>;
13. <http://szolomag-orlemeny.biomax.hu/>
14. http://www.anpc.gov.ro/anpcfpt/legislatie/or_din_8_140116.pdf;
15. <http://stiri.covasnamedia.ro/2017/02/statiune-a-covasna-a-atras-aproape-jumatate-din-numarul-turistilor-care-au-vizitat-judetul-anul-trecut/>;
16. <http://www.transilvaniatravel.com/romania/azare-covasna>;
17. http://www.sfatulmedicului.ro/Educatie-pentru-sanatate/ghid-practic-de-estimare-a-portiilor_12079;
18. <https://dozadesanatate.ro/samburii-de-struguri-beneficii/>.

COMPARATIVE STUDY REGARDING THE ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY OF SUBCRITICAL EXTRACTS FROM VITIS SEMEN, MUSTARD AND POLYGONUM CUSPIDATUM

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Abstract: *Extraction at subcritical pressures of bioactive compounds from plants in soft extraction conditions represents an alternative to replace classical methods of extraction with different solvents, or on enzyme basis. The most important advantage that the HFC extractors with liquefied gas at subcritical pressure offer is that they may extract oils in pure estate, at room temperature and in the absence of air, which allows to create new categories of products with a wide range of bioactive substances as, for example, from the group of alimentary aromas and, respectively, from the series of parfumes, pharmaceutical products etc.*

The paper presents a comparative study of antioxidant activity of different extracts (Vitis semen, Mustard (seeds) and Polygonum Cuspidatum (root parts)), measured through electrochemical detection by using a biosensor.

Keywords: *antioxidant activity, subcritical extraction, Vitis Semen, Mustard, Polygonum Cuspidatum*

1. Introduction

The scope of the project is to find the best extraction method for the bioactive compounds, such antioxidants, polyphenols, anthocyanins, and to find certain utilization in food products. Part of them has to be extracted by using subcritical extraction with HFC 134a. Preliminary results show that the quality and total amount of bio-compounds is higher than classical extraction. Supercritical fluid extraction (SFE) technology has become an increasingly popular method for the recovery of food ingredients and products over the last 20 years, due to its unique advantages, including low temperature use, selective extraction, simpler and cleaner (solvent-free) product recovery.

SFE is also an environmentally benign technology since the process typically generates no waste. Supercritical fluid exhibits high density like liquids, which contributes to greater potential for solubilisation of materials, and low viscosity similar to gases, which enables its penetration into the solid [3].

Recent researches was done by combining the two methods. In the first stage lipids were extracted on HFC extractor (FC 100, Timatic, Italy), then second phase extracts hydrosoluble compounds in SLE extractor (MiniTimatic, Italy).

In this case, extraction efficiency was higher 20-30%-and time was reduced between 32-35 %, also depending on temperature (which was varying between 30-40C degrees). Better results were obtained by applying ultrasound waves in extraction liquid in the second phase. Also, combinations of glycerin, propilen-glycol, alcohol has to be use. The main phases of the technological process that has to be optimized are: drying, sterilizing, chopping, liposoluble extraction, hydrosoluble extraction with variable pH, filtering and purification of extracts, packaging [1, 2, 4].

Various methods for characterization or analytical evaluation of preservatives and antioxidants have been explored and applied. Alongside chromatographic or spectrophotometric alternatives, knowledge of the redox and amperometric behaviour, the electrochemical assessment can be a basis to explain useful properties or a direct analytical pathway in dosage of the additives in mixture or individual systems. Electrochemistry of various natural antioxidants is the subject of a active research as is the electrochemical study of the phenolic compounds or their derivatives.

2. Materials and methods

The raw material studied was: *Vitis semen*, Mustard (seeds) and *Polygonum Cuspidatum* (root parts)). Extraction from raw materials was done with FC 100 extractor (Timatic, Italy) by using HFC 134a (1,1,1,2-tetrafluoroethane) at pressure 5-8 bar and temperature 5-35 C degrees.

The extracts were diluted at 3 different concentration: 20, 40, 60 μ l in pH7 ws. Biosensors are gaining an increasing role in food analysis; they can be defined as a sub-group of chemical systems, in which the analytical device includes a biological sensor coupled with a chemical or physical transducer.

Fig. 1 Extractor TIMATIC FC100

The biosensor used in this study was based on the electrochemical measure of potential to determine concentration of analytes or to characterize the chemical reactivity of a compound. Differential Pulse Voltammetry (DPV) has been used for quantification, since it is suitable to measure the redox properties of chemical compounds having low molecular weights [7, 10].

Applying a potential, a redox reaction occurs on working electrode surface; electrons involved in the reaction modify the current applied in the cell, and this modification is elaborated by a signal transducer. Results obtained with biosensors were compared for 3 different extracts from different 3 raw materials.

3. Results and discussions

Antioxidant activity of samples was measured by an electrochemical biosensor,

EDEL meter (Edel Therapeutics, Lausanne, Switzerland) . This is an analytical device, which includes a biological detector coupled with a chemical transducer and specific software. Gallic acid was used as a reference standard.

Each sample, standard solutions or diluted extract samples, was transferred in an aluminium-wrapped becker under magnetic stirring. Then, the electrode was inserted in the EDEL meter and immersed in the solutions. After 10 second, the software was launched and measurements, expressed in nA, were recorded each 30s.

For each sample, the measure was stopped when EDEL values were stable, reaching the plateau status. In figure 2, 3, 4 can be observed the comparative results of the antioxidant activity of *Vitis semen*, *Mustard*, *Polygonum Cuspidatum*, evaluated through the intensity of the current between electrodes [nA].

Fig. 2 Antioxidant activity of *Vitis semen*, evaluated through intensity of the current between electrodes [nA]

Fig. 3 Antioxidant activity of *Mustard*, evaluated through intensity of the current between electrodes [nA]

Fig. 4 Antioxidant activity of *Polygonum Cuspidatum*, evaluated through intensity of the current between electrodes [nA]

Conclusions

This contribution accentuates the role of electrochemical techniques in the determination of antioxidant activity/capacity in the biological samples of plant origin and in clinical samples. Electrochemical techniques represent due to selectivity and sensitivity suitable tool for the determination of antioxidant capacity in biological samples, where these method are sensitive under the low concentrations of antioxidants.

The preliminary data obtained with this method showed a high variability in the antioxidant activity of samples, in particular for *Polygonum Cuspidatum*.

The best results was observed in the case of *Mustard*, were after 10 -15 tests, correlation between the concentration of extract and the intensity of the current remain significant.

References

1. Ceballos C., Fernandez H. The Electroanalytical Determination of Antioxidants in Corn Oil Using Ultramicroelectrodes. J. Braz. Chem. Soc. 1995;6:1-5;
2. Diaz T.G., Cabanillas A.G., Franco M.F.A., Salinas F., Vire J.-C. Voltammetric Behavior and Simultaneous Determination of the Antioxidants Propyl Gallate, Butylated Hydroxyanisole, and Butylated Hydroxytoluene in Acidic Acetonitrile-Water Medium Using PLS Calibration. Electroanalysis. 1998;10:497-505;
3. Giacomelli C., Giacomelli F.C., Alves L.O., Timbola A.K., Spinelli A. Electrochemistry of Vitamin E Hydro-Alcoholic Solutions. J. Braz. Chem. Soc. 2004;15:748-755;
4. Korotkova E.I., Avramchik O.A., Angelov T.M., Karabainov Y.A. Investigation of antioxidant activity and lipophilicity parameters of some preservatives. Electrochim. 2005;51:324-332;
5. Litescu S.-C., Radu G.-L. Estimation of the antioxidative properties of tocopherols—an electrochemical approach. Eur. Food Res. Technol. 2000;211:218-221;

6. Livingstone D.J., Ford M.G., Huuskonen J.J., Salt D.W. Simultaneous prediction solubility and octanol/water partition coefficient based on descriptors derived from molecular structure. *J. Comp. - Aid. Molec. Des.* 2001;15:741–752;
7. Mannino S., Brenna O., Buratti S., Cosio M.S. A new method for the evaluation of the “antioxidant power” of wines. *Electroanalysis.* 1998;10:908–912;
8. Morrow G.W. *Organic Electrochemistry*. 3rd Edition. Publisher: Marcel Dekker Inc.; New York, USA: 1991. pp. 589–611;
9. Oprea O.B., Comparative studies regarding the use of Grape Seed Powder (GSP) in bakery products, *Journal of EcoAgriTourism*, Vol. 13, no.1 2017, pg. 34-41;
10. Psotova J., Zahalkova J., Hrbac J., Simanek V., Bartek J. Determination of Total Antioxidant Capacity in Plasma by Cyclic Voltammetry. Two Case Reports. *Biomed. Papers.* 2001;145:81–83;
11. Saad B., Bari Md. F., Saleh M. I., Ahmad K., Tolib M.K.M. Simultaneous determination of preservatives (benzoic acid, sorbic acid, methylparaben and propylparaben) in foodstuffs using high-performance liquid chromatography. *J. Chromaogr.* 2005;1073:393–397;
12. Wang J., Deo R.P., Musameh M. Stable and Sensitive Electrochemical Detection of Phenolic Compounds at Carbon Nanotube Modified Glassy Carbon Electrodes. *Electroanalysis.* 2003;15:1830–1834.

ASSESSMENT METHOD FOR HYGIENIC DESIGN IN FOOD INDUSTRY. WATER DRAINAGE AND WATER SAVING STUDY CASE

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Abstract: *The new trends in consumer asking — starting from minimally processed and reduced additive/preservative foods, to pre-prepared ready-to-eat/ready-to-cook food—are placing enormous pressures on all food producers, not only to innovate but to remain on top of food safety challenges. Food producers must be sure that their products are protected throughout production by restricting access and controlling conditions for survival of microorganisms, foreign bodies, pests, and chemical contaminants such as lubricants or biocides. This paper presents the assessment method used by EHEDG (European Hygienic Engineering and Design Group) and some results obtained, as study case for Water drainage and water saving study case. By using hygienic designed equipment and hygienic facility design into the operation at the same level of importance as Good Manufacturing Practices (GMPs) and Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Point (HACCP) programs, food manufacturers not only significantly reduce potential food safety hazards but can obtain energy, water, and cost-savings.*

Keywords: *assessment method in food safety, hygienic design*

1. Introduction

For nearly 30 years, EHEDG has led the way in guiding the food industry in hygienic design solutions by offering practical guidelines, test procedures, training and education. To develop a comprehensive food production hygiene toolkit, EHEDG garners knowledge from the practical experience of food and beverage processors, the technical expertise of equipment and component manufacturers, and the scientific findings of respected academic and research institutes. This information translates into EHEDG's best practices resource portfolio that includes industry guidelines, hygienic equipment certification, and training workshops.

EHEDG provides food manufacturers with science-based but practically oriented guidelines and other resources for applying hygienic design and engineering principles in their plants.

2. Method for evaluation

During last decades EHEDG developed a series of test methods, in order to evaluate hygienic and aseptic appropriateness for equipment. These are not intended to indicate performance in specific applications. The results

of these tests provide documentation and guidance on the selection of hygienic and/or aseptic equipment. The onus still rests with the food manufacturer to develop suitable cleaning regimes particular to a process.

Current test methods include:

- In-place cleanability of small and moderately sized closed equipment
- Steam sterilisability
- Bacteria tightness

The list of institutes and organisations which are authorised by EHEDG to test and certify equipment by the use of the EHEDG logo can be found here: <https://www.ehedg.org/testing-certification/test-certification-institutes/>

Both open and closed equipment used in food processing environments can be certified. EHEDG maintains a list of all equipment that has been certified. Although there are no limitations on the complexity of the piece of equipment, typically only small, individual components are certified rather than large, complex machines or processing systems.

For certification of open equipment, ALL equipment surfaces are evaluated as product contact surfaces and must meet all hygienic design criteria in relevant EHEDG guidelines.

Currently, only closed equipment with pipe connections between 25 mm O.D. and 75 mm O.D. can be tested due to limitations of CIP testing.

In general, all sizes of the same piece of equipment must be evaluated with a design review and CIP tested prior to certification. However, in a few instances where equipment designs are considered completely scalable by an EHEDG Authorized Test Institute, testing of only one size can be used for certification of the entire range. In most instances, equipment is NOT completely scalable. Currently, the only alternative to testing each size is to perform computational fluid dynamics modeling (CFD) of the different designs to select the size for testing that may be the most difficult to clean based on wall shear stresses and fluid exchange in critical areas. If this characteristic size passes CIP testing, the sizes with higher wall shear stresses and fluid exchange in critical areas may also be considered for certification and listed on the same certificate.

All closed pieces of equipment which are installed in a pipeline, e.g. pumps, valves, and inline sensors, must be tested according to the method of EHEDG Doc. 2. This test is a screening test for hygienic design and identifies areas that may contain a crevice which can trap soil and microorganisms or are not easily cleaned due to the flow dynamics.

Closed equipment which fully comply with the hygienic design requirements can be certified without testing. Examples are pipe lines or pressure sensors without elastomeric seals.

The method of assessing the in-place cleanability of food processing equipment is described in EHEDG Document 2 published by EHEDG. The test method is used as a basic screening test for hygienic design. It is used to determine if areas (or features) within a piece of equipment are “easily cleanable” by comparing the test results to that of a standard reference pipe soiled and cleaned during the same test. Due to inherent variability in the cleaning of equipment, the test must be repeated successfully at least 3 times for equipment to be eligible for certification. This test is required for equipment to be certified as Type EL Class I and EL Aseptic Class I.

EL Class I is only for closed equipment, intended to be cleaned-in-place (CIP) with liquids, and can be CIP tested using the method of Doc. 2. EL Class I AUX is for certification of auxiliary open equipment which is intended to be

cleaned-in-place with liquids but not tested. EL Class II is for equipment which is intended to be cleaned with liquids but must be disassembled or dismantled prior to cleaning.

Since open equipment cannot currently be tested to ensure cleanability, open equipment intended to be cleaned with liquids can only be certified as EL Class I AUX or EL Class II. Open equipment intended to be dry cleaned only can be certified as ED Class I or Class II.

Different elastomers may have different material properties. Experience has shown that different materials in the same mechanical design may affect the equipment cleanability. Since 2009 the certificate lists the elastomers that were CIP tested. The equipment is only certified when used with the elastomers listed on the certificate. Each elastomer listed on the certificate must be CIP tested using the method of Doc. 2

For closed equipment components intended to be cleaned in-place (CIP) with liquids (EL CLASS I certified), only the internal, wetted surfaces/parts are evaluated and certified to meet the hygienic design criteria according to EHEDG guidelines. This means that for pumps, valves and in-line sensors; the motor, drive, actuator or frame (if present) are NOT evaluated and certified for cleanability according to EHEDG guidelines. Only the internal, product contact surfaces are evaluated and certified according to EHEDG guidelines and, if necessary, tested for easy cleanability according to Doc. 2.

EHEDG only allows metal to metal joints for equipment subject to certification under Type EL Class II and Type ED Class I and II. As they may harbor soil or liquids and could corrode, EHEDG does not recommend any direct metal to metal joints other than welding.

3. Procedure for HD evaluation

Every piece of equipment (open and closed) considered for certification must be evaluated by one of the EHEDG Authorized Test Institutes. All evaluations will include a “Design Review” and most closed equipment will require cleanability testing according to EHEDG Doc. 2. For a design review, a new sample of the equipment is compared to official drawings provided by the manufacturer and to the appropriate EHEDG guidelines. For example, a pump will be reviewed for compliance with EHEDG guidelines 8, 9, 10, 16, 17, 23, 25, 32 and 35. During the review, certain design features will also be measured and verified, e.g. surface

roughness and internal radii. After the design review, the equipment may be recommended for re-design due to deviations from the EHEDG guidelines. Some deviations from the hygienic design criteria in the guidelines may be allowable if deemed "technically unavoidable" for the particular device to function properly. After a successful design review, open equipment may be submitted directly for certification but most closed equipment will require testing for cleanability according to EHEDG Doc. 2. Only after successfully completing at least 3 CIP tests, will the closed equipment be eligible for certification.

Evaluation and cleanability testing for equipment cleaned with liquids (Type EL) proceed using the following steps, published in this Evaluation Procedure (PDF).

For Type ED, the procedure is based only on a design review using the following steps in this Evaluation Procedure (PDF)

Equipment which is considered to comply with the EHEDG guidelines following a design review and CIP testing (if appropriate) by an EHEDG Authorized Test Institute can be submitted for EHEDG certification. A certification file will be completed by one of the EHEDG Authorized Test and Certification Institutes and reviewed by at least one other Authorized Institute before being accepted by EHEDG. Since open equipment and dry cleaned equipment cannot currently be tested, these certification files must be reviewed by all of the EHEDG Authorized Institutes prior to certification. After successful review of a certification file and acceptance of the terms of the EHEDG contract for use of the logo, a "Certificate of Compliance" will be issued and the equipment will be included in the list of certified equipment on the EHEDG website. EHEDG has published a certification procedure for better understanding of the whole process.

4. Results

As a results of the EHEDG method assessment applying, many companies improved their technical solution in different are they are working in.

Below are some improvement made by ACO **drainage system** producer:

- The drainage system is designed in accordance with the best practice hygienic design principles specified by the European Hygienic Engineering & Design Group (EHEDG). This means, for example, that corners such be rounded with a minimum radii of 3mm, welds must be continuous and not be made on corners or overlapped, and the surface of the drainage needs to be smooth with a roughness factor of 0.3 to 0.5 micro-metres.

- The drainage is made from stainless steel of Grade 304, 316 or higher. When it comes to food safety, the only real option when specifying a drainage solution is one constructed from stainless steel. Stainless steel is easier to clean and to keep clean than systems made from other materials such as plastic or iron. Consider operating conditions such as acidity and temperature as well as the cleaning methodology you want to adopt when deciding which grade of stainless steel to use.

- The stainless steel drainage system should be fully pickle passivated to minimise corrosion and pitting. This is a key recommendation of EHEDG and fabricators that don't fully pickle passivate their products run the risk of failing to meet longer term durability requirements as well as compromising hygiene.

Regarding **water saving**, can be mentioned the Ecodhybat project. According to 2006 European Commission data, water consumption in the European food production sector represents 12 percent of total industrial water consumption, with sanitation cited as the main reason for water use in most food sectors.¹ On the other hand, water used for sanitation becomes wastewater, which contains food residues (organic load) and cleaning agents such as acid, alkali, detergents and disinfectants. The main pollutants found in wastewater are organic matter (e.g. chemical or biological oxygen demand [COD, BOD]), oils and fats, suspended solids, nitrate, chloride, phosphates, ammonium and nutrients as nitrogen and phosphorous. In general, the food and drink sector is considered one of the largest producers of wastewater.

Table 1 summarises the results obtained in terms of water savings during cleaning when comparing the hygienic version with the conventional one.

Table 1. Percentage of water savings

Facility	Equipment	Water savings (%)
Dairy	Sterile tank 30000 L (lid)	40
Dairy	Tank cleaning device (SSB vs. RSJ), tank 7000 L	42
Dairy	Eq. packaging disposal (interior)	75
Dairy	Eq. packaging disposal (exterior)	9
Dairy	Conveyor belt	37
Fish plant	Batter tank system	96
Fish plant	Viscosity measurement system	83
Fish plant	Batter mix pumping system	27
AINIA	Sensor	38
AINIA	Centrifugal pump	39
AINIA	T-piece 60 AINIA Load cell	29

Conclusions

Hygienic processing is a sine qua non requirement for the food industry. Because of this, food producers devote a lot of time and resources to reach the required cleaning and disinfection level, among other preventive measures. Any surface in contact with food should be sanitized to reach an appropriate safe and hygienic standard. This study shows that hygienic design reduces environmental impacts related to sanitation of equipment and installations – from water, energy and chemical products, to wastewater and CO₂ emissions – and consequently, can positively contribute to a cost reduction in the industrial activity. Overall, a 48 percent water savings was obtained when cleaning the hygienically designed equipment.

References

1. Directive 98/37/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 June 1998 on the approximation of the laws of the Member States relating to machinery (Machinery Directive);
2. Council Directive 89/109/EEC of 21 December 1988 on the approximation of the laws of the Member States relating to materials and articles intended to come into contact with foodstuffs;
3. Corrosion Resistant Alloys (1983). Publ. No. 3783, Inco Alloys International Ltd, Holmer Road, Hereford, England HR4 9SL;
4. AISI Steel Products Manual, Stainless and Heat Resisting Steels, December 1974, Table 2-1, pp. 18-19. American Iron and Steel Institute, 1000 16 th St, NW, Washington, DC 20036 . (www.steel.org);
5. EN 17 440: 2001. Stainless steels - Technical delivery conditions for drawn wire;
6. Alloy Designations for Cast Stainless Steels. ASTM Standard A781/A781M, Appendix XI. Steel Founder's Society of America, Cast Metal Federation Bldg., 455 State St, Des Plaines, IL 60016, USA;
7. J. Holah and H.L.M. Lelieveld, Hygienic Design of Food Factories, Woodhead Publishing Series in Food Science, Technology and Nutrition, ISBN: 978-1-84569-564-4;
8. **** EHEDG Yearbook 2017/2018;
9. **** www.ehedg.org.